

**The EUMETSAT Satellite Application Facility on
Land Surface Analysis**

Validation Report

EPS/AVHRR

Vegetation Parameters Data Record (VEGA-R)

ETFVC-R (LSA-455), ETLAI-R (LSA-456), ETFAPAR-R (LSA-457)

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List of Acronyms

AVHRR	Advanced Very-High-Resolution Radiometer
ASCAT	Advanced SCATterometer
APU	Accuracy, Precision, Uncertainty
B	Mean bias
BQ	Best Quality
BRDF	Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function
BRF	Bidirectional Reflectance Factor
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
C6.1	Collection 6.1
Cal/Val	Calibration and Validation
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellite
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CUL	Cultivated
GBOV	Ground-Based Observations for Validation
GPR	Gaussian Process Regression
CYCLOPES	Cyclically Ordered Phase Sequence
DBF	Deciduous Broadleaf Forest
DHP	Digital Hemispherical Photography
DOY	Day Of Year
DR	Data Record
EBF	Evergreen Broadleaf Forest
EO	Earth Observation
EOLAB	Earth Observation LABORatory
EPS	EUMETSAT Polar System
ESA	European Space Agency
ETAL	EPS 10-Days Albedo
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
FAPAR	Fraction of AbsorbedPhotosynthetically Active Radiation

FVC	Fraction of Vegetation Cover
FRM4Veg	Fiducial Reference Measurements for Vegetation
GBOV	Ground-Based Observations for Validation
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GPR	Gaussian Processes Regression
HER	Herbaceous
IPMA	Instituto Portugues do Mare da Atmosfera
LAI	Leaf Area Index
LANDVAL	LAND VALidation network
LP	Land Product
LPV	Land Product Validation Subgroup
LSA SAF	Land Surface Analysis Satellite Applications Facility
MAD	Median Absolute Deviation
MAR	Major Axis Regression
MD	Median Deviation
MetOp	Meteorological Operational
MODIS	Moderate Resolution ImagingSpectroradiometer
MOD15A2H	MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index/FPAR 8-Day Global 500m SIN Grid
N	Number of samples
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NEON	National Ecological Observatory Network
NIR	Near-infrared
NLF	Needle Leaf Forest
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OF	Other Forests
OLIVE	On Line Validation Exercise
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
PUM	Product User Manual

PROBA-V	Project for On-Board Autonomy-Vegetation
PROSAIL	PROSPECT+SAIL Coupled model
PROSPECT	leaf optical PROPERTIESPECTra
R	Pearson linear correlation coefficient
RM	Reference Measurement
RMSD	Root Mean Square Deviation
RTM	Radiative Transfer Model
STD	Standard deviation
SAIL	Scattering by Arbitrarily Inclined Leaves
SAVS	Surface Albedo Validation Sites
SBA	Sparse vegetated and Bare Areas
SHR	Shrublands
SPOT /VGT	Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre / VEGETATION
UV	University of Valencia
Vx	Version x
VEGA	FVC, LAI and FAPAR VEGEtAtion Products
VEGA-R	VEGA DR
VIS	Visible
WGCV	Working Group on Calibration and Validation (CEOS)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Satellite Application Facility (SAF) on Land Surface Analysis (LSA) is part of the SAF Network, a set of specialized development and processing centres, serving as European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) distributed Applications Ground Segment. The SAF network complements the product-oriented activities at the EUMETSAT Central Facility in Darmstadt. The main purpose of the LSA SAF is to take full advantage of remotely sensed data, particularly those available from EUMETSAT sensors, to measure land surface variables, which will find primarily applications in meteorology (<http://lsa-saf.eumetsat.int>). The EUMETSAT Polar System (EPS) is Europe's first polar orbiting operational meteorological satellite program and the European contribution to a joint polar system with the U.S. EUMETSAT will have the operational responsibility for the “morning orbit” with Meteorological Operational (MetOp) satellites, the first of which was successfully launched on October 19, 2006. Despite the wide range of sensors on-board MetOp (<http://www.eumetsat.int/>), most LSA SAF parameters make use of the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) and, to a lesser extent, of the Advanced Scatterometer (ASCAT).

This report presents the validation results of LSA SAF EPS vegetation data record (VEGA-R), spanning 2007 to mid 2021, derived from AVHRR observations aboard the MetOp-A (2007-2014) and MetOp-B (2015-mid 2021) satellites. This data record is derived from the latest version of the near real time (NRT) algorithm. Products are delivered at a ten-day time step based on EPS albedo Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) products. The suite of LSA SAF EPS vegetation (VEGA-R) products are the leaf area index (ETLAI-R), the fraction of photosynthetically active radiation absorbed by vegetation (ETFAPAR-R) and the fractional vegetation cover (ETFVC-R). The algorithm is based on a hybrid method which combines the generalization level of physically-based radiative transfer models with the flexibility and computational efficiency of advanced non-parametric regression methods. The quality assessment is performed in agreement with community-agree-upon good practices for validation of global LAI satellite products proposed within the Committee on Earth Observation Satellite (CEOS) Working Group on Calibration and Validation (WGCV) Land Product Validation (LPV) subgroup. Several criteria are evaluated including product completeness, spatial and temporal consistency, accuracy, precision (inter- and intra-annual), uncertainty, stability and the conformity with LSA SAF requirements on accuracy. The consistency between MetOp-A and MetOp-B retrievals as well as with NRT products is also assessed. Product intercomparisons are performed using as reference the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) 1 km V1 LAI, FAPAR and FVC products, based on SPOT/VGT and PROBA-V observations, NASA MODIS Collection 6.1 LAI and FAPAR, and Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) FAPAR V3, which is also based on SPOT/VGT and PROBA-V. For the product intercomparisons, a global network of 720 land validation (LANDVAL) sites is used. For direct

validation with ground references, the CEOS-endorsed DIRECT 2.1 database of upscaled values, and the Copernicus Ground-Based Observations for Validation (GBOV) upscaled land products V2.0 are used.

The evaluation of EPS VEGA data record has shown in overall good quality as compared to both satellite-based and ground-based references. EPS VEGA shows remarkably good consistency in the comparison with CLMS V1 (RMSD of 0.08, 0.46 and 0.07 for FVC, LAI and FAPAR) over LANDVAL sites (2013-2016), displaying some underestimation over NLF sites and lower agreement with the MODIS products, mainly over EBF sites for LAI and NLF for FAPAR (in both cases showing EPS underestimation). The poorest agreement was found with the C3S FAPAR products, which showed the lowest accuracy when compared to ground-based references. EPS VEGA data record present reliable seasonal and inter-annual variations, with larger discrepancies observed at the end of the growing season (EPS product tends to display longer seasons compared to satellite reference products). The EPS VEGA record exhibits inter-annual and intra-annual precision comparable to the reference products over the entire period, except for a reduction in inter-annual precision observed for the first two years, which is directly attributable to the lower quality of the input data in 2007. The accuracy assessment with ground data shows RMSD about 0.12-0.14 for FVC, 0.77-0.87 for LAI and 0.12-0.14 for FAPAR depending on the ground database, improving the accuracy of FVC and LAI of reference satellite products. EPS VEGA data record shows no impact due to the transition from MetOp-A (2007-2014) to MetOp-B (2015-2021), and demonstrate high temporal stability, as compared to MODIS products. EPS VEGA-R clearly outperforms the CLMS V1 and C3S V3 data records stability, both derived from SPOT/VGT and PROBA-V. EPS VEGA-R meets the LSA SAF target accuracy requirement for more than 50% of the retrievals when compared with global reference datasets, and achieves the threshold requirement for up to 80% of the GBOV ground-based data and up to 92% of the CLMS V1 satellite-based reference, demonstrating its good overall accuracy performance. EPS VEGA-R is fully consistent with the NRT products with no bias and showing 99% of samples within target accuracy level, enabling its complementary use to extend the time series up to the present. However, user should exercise caution during the first months of the data record (2007), as higher-than-expected values were detected in calibration sites due to lower input data quality during that period.

1 BACKGROUND OF THE DOCUMENT

1.1 OBJECTIVE

The objective of this document is to evaluate the quality of the EPS FVC, LAI and FAPAR vegetation (VEGA) Data Record (VEGA-R) (ETFVC-R, ETLAI-R, ETFAPAR-R) produced for the 01/2007 to 06/2021 period derived from MetOp-A to MetOp-B, with particular attention to the stability and consistency of the time series due to the transition from MetOp-A to MetOp-B. The conformity of LSA SAF accuracy requirements is evaluated against ground-based references and satellite-based references from other Earth Observation (EO) services.

1.2 RELATED DOCUMENTS

The following documents are baseline references for the LSA SAF products:

- [RD-1] García-Haro, F.J.; Campos-Taberner, M.; Camacho, F. Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for EPS/AVHRR Vegetation parameters (ETFVC, ETLAI, ETFAPAR), Ref: SAF/LAND/UV/ATBD_EPSVEGA/1.0, 10/07/2017.
- [RD-2] Fuster, B.; Sánchez-Zapero, J.; Camacho, F.; García-Haro, F.J. Validation Report of EPS/AVHRR Vegetation Parameters (ETFVC, ETLAI, ETFAPAR). Ref: SAF/LAND/UV/VR_EPSVEGA/1.2, 30/07/2019.
- [RD-3] Météo-France/CNRM. Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Ten-day Surface Albedo from EPS/Metop/AVHRR (ETAL, ETAL-R). Ref: SAF/LAND/MF/ATBD ETAL/1.5, 13/10/2022.
- [RD-4] García-Haro, F.J.; Campos-Taberner, M.; Camacho, F. Product User Manual of EPS/AVHRR Vegetation parameters (ETFVC, ETLAI, ETFAPAR), Ref: SAF/LAND/UV/PUM_EPSVEGA/1.1, 06/03/2018

2 LSA SAF PRODUCTS

The algorithm for retrieving FVC, LAI and FAPAR from EPS data relies on the inversion of the PROSAIL radiative transfer model (RTM), which results from coupling the PROSPECT (Jacquemoud and Baret, 1990) and the SAIL (Verhoef, 1984) models with a family of multi-output machine learning retrieval methods (García-Haro et al., 2018). The PROSAIL RTM is used for generating a large training database comprising the biophysical variables (i.e., LAI, FVC, FAPAR, the retrieval outputs) and the atmospherically corrected cloud-cleared k_0 parameter of the BRDF on the EPS Channel 1 (VIS 0.6), Channel 2 (VIS 0.8) and Channel 3 (MIR 1.6) (the retrieval inputs). A novel multi-output Gaussian Processes Regression (GPR_{multi}) is applied to retrieve LAI, FVC and FAPAR maps globally from corresponding EPS surface reflectance data. The global EPS products include uncertainty estimates taking into account the uncertainty of retrieval method and input errors propagation (García-Haro et al., 2018). The present version of the algorithm is fully described in the algorithm theoretical basis document [RD-1]. The validation results of the EPS VEGA near-real time products are described in the validation report [RD-2].

- **Description of the data set evaluated**

This report evaluates the MetOp/AVHRR vegetation products data record (EPS VEGA-R: ETFVC-R, ETLAI-R, ETFAPAR-R) version 1.0 delivered at a ten-day time step based on albedo BRDF products [RD-3] for the period 01/2007 - 06/2021. This Data Record (DR) was obtained with the best version of its equivalent NRT products (ETFVC, ETLAI, ETFAPAR) which can also complement the time series from mid-2021 onwards.

The AVHRR-based vegetation products are generated pixel-by-pixel, maintaining the original resolution of level 3 ETAL product. They are rectified images in sinusoidal projection centred at (0°N, 0°W), with a resolution of 1.1 km × 1.1 km. The timeslot in the filename of this product corresponds to the last day of the 20-day time-compositing period. For example, the filename HDF5_LSASAF_M02-AVHR_ETLAI_GLOBE_200804250000 with day of production 25 of April corresponds to the period from 6 to 25 April 2008. It should be noted that M02 refers to data MetOp-A, whereas M01 refers to MetOp-B. Data from MetOp-A covers from January 2007 to December 2014, whereas data from MetOp-B covers from January 2015 to December 2020. The EPS FVC, LAI and FAPAR DR contain 4 datasets each comprising: (1) a vegetation variable estimate, (2) an error estimate, (3) a quality flag (QF) information and (4) the “age” (Z_{age}) of the information (Z_{age}), representing the mean of the “age” (in days) of the observations used to fit the BRDF model (see details in the product user manual, [RD-4]).

It should be noted that to improve the agreement between Metop-A and Metop-B a shift of one pixel (0.01°) in longitudes is applied in case of Metop-B, being the top left corner coordinate considered for Metop-B of -179.99° instead of -180°.

3 PRODUCT REQUIREMENTS

This section reviews the LSA SAF product requirements with particular attention to the accuracy and stability requirements.

- Accuracy is the degree of the “closeness of the agreement between the result of a measurement and a true value of the measurand” (JCGM, 2014).
- Temporal stability is defined as the ability of a data record to detect long-term trends (GCOS-200, 2016).

The LSA SAF accuracy requirement for EPS VEGA-R products are defined for optimal, target and threshold levels as shown in Table 1. This report evaluates the conformity of EPS VEGA-R with respect to each of these levels. The verification method defined by LSA SAF specifies that compliance with the target level (i.e., $|\text{bias}| < \text{target}$) must be achieved for at least 50% of the retrievals as compared to reference (satellite-based and ground-based) datasets. Note that the optimal level for LAI is expressed only as a relative value, and then for very low values it would be very difficult to meet this level (almost impossible considering product uncertainties).

Table 1. LSA SAF Product Requirements on accuracy for FVC, LAI and FAPAR EPS/AVHRR products.

Variable	Optimal	Target	Threshold
FVC	Max [0.05, 10%]	Max [0.075, 15%]	Max [0.1, 20%]
LAI	15%	Max [0.5, 20%]	Max [0.75, 25%]
FAPAR	Max [0.05, 10%]	Max [0.075, 15%]	Max [0.1, 20%]

No specific requirements for the stability of VEGA-R time series are currently defined within the LSA SAF service. Consequently, its compliance cannot be formally evaluated in this report, although the stability of the data record is examined in the following sections. For reference, GCOS (GCOS-245, 2022) specifies stability requirements of less than 3% per decade for FAPAR and less than 6% per decade for LAI products at threshold level.

4 VALIDATION METHODS AND REFERENCE DATASETS

4.1 VALIDATION PROTOCOL

The protocols and metrics used for this quality evaluation exercise were defined to be consistent with satellite product validation good practices proposed by the land product validation subgroup of the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) working group on calibration and validation (so called CEOS LPV). Several criteria of performance were assessed in agreement with previous global LAI validation exercises (Camacho et al., 2013; Fuster et al., 2020; Garrigues et al., 2008; Weiss et al., 2007), the On Line Validation Exercise (OLIVE) tool, developed in the framework of CEOS LPV to standardize validation results (Weiss et al., 2014), the CEOS LPV LAI product validation protocol (Fernandes et al., 2014) and additional metrics proposed for a standardized validation of bio-geophysical products (Camacho et al., 2025).

The proposed methodology relies on direct validation and product intercomparison approaches.

- The direct validation is computed against DIRECT V2.1 ground data set (see section 4.3.1) up-scaled according with the CEOS LPV recommendations (Fernandes et al., 2014) and the Ground-Based Observations for Validation (GBOV, see section 4.3.2) of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS).
- Intercomparisons with similar remote sensing products (see section 4.2) can determine whether the products behave similarly in space and time on a global scale and allow us to identify differences between products to be investigated in more detail in order to diagnose product anomalies and devise algorithm refinements. The LANDVAL network of sites (Fuster et al., 2020; Sánchez-Zapero et al., 2023, 2020) is used for sampling global conditions in the intercomparison with similar satellite products. The LANDVAL network is composed of 720 sites (Figure 1), of which 521 sites are from Surface Albedo Validation Sites (SAVS 1.0) (Loew et al., 2016). The LANDVAL sampling is complemented with 20 desert calibration sites (Lacherade et al., 2013) and additional sites in order to cover under-sampled regions and biome types. These analyses are achieved per aggregated land cover class based on the 8 generic classes: Evergreen Broadleaf Forest (EBF, 9.6% of LANDVAL sites), Deciduous Broadleaf Forest (DBF, 7.5%), Needle-Leaf Forest (NLF, 11.3%), Other Forests (OF, 8.8%), Cultivated (CUL, 19.5%), Herbaceous (HER, 21.3%), Shrublands (SHR, 8.2%) and Sparse and Bare areas (SBA, 13.8%). LANDVAL was recently upgraded to include up to 2,000 sites (LANDVAL V2) to improve its global representativeness (Martínez-Sánchez et al., 2024). However, at the time of this exercise, the reference datasets for the LANDVAL V2 sites covering the entire period were not yet available. Therefore, the previous version was used instead. LANDVAL V2 will be employed in subsequent validation upgrades.

Figure 1 illustrates the sampling used for product direct validation (DIRECT 2.1 + GBOV) and product intercomparison (LANDVAL).

Figure 1. Sampling used for direct validation (DIRECT 2.1 + GBOV V2) and product intercomparison (LANDVAL).

The following criteria of performance and metrics are assessed to evaluate VEGA-R products:

Product Completeness

Completeness corresponds to the absence of spatial and temporal gaps in the data. Missing data are mainly due to cloud or snow contamination, poor atmospheric conditions or technical problems during the acquisition of the images and is generally considered by users as a severe limitation of a given product. It is therefore mandatory to document the completeness of the product (i.e. the distribution in space and time of missing data). Global maps of missing values and the monthly distribution of gaps over LANDVAL network of sites are displayed.

Spatial Consistency

Spatial consistency refers to the realism and repeatability of the spatial distribution of retrievals over the globe.

A first qualitative check of the realism and repeatability of spatial distribution of retrievals and the absence of strange patterns or artefacts (e.g., missing values, stripes, unrealistic low values, geolocation issue, etc.) is achieved through systematic visual analysis of all global maps and zooms based on the expert knowledge of the scientist.

The spatial consistency can be quantitatively assessed by comparing the spatial distribution of a reference validated product with the product biophysical maps under study. Two products are considered spatially consistent when the residuals are within the uncertainty requirements of the variable. The residual (ε) is estimated assuming a linear trend between two products ($Y = aX + b + \varepsilon$), then the residual can be written as $\varepsilon = Y - aX - b$, which represent the remaining discrepancies regarding the general trend between both products. In this way, systematic trends are not considered, depicting more clearly patterns associated to the spatial distribution of retrievals.

The methodology for visual analysis includes the visualization of animations of global maps at a reduced (1/6 pixels) resolution. The product content, including physical retrievals and its ancillary layers, is checked.

Maps and histograms of residuals, at a reduced (1/6 pixels) resolution, between the product under study and satellite-based reference products are analysed to identify regions showing spatial inconsistencies for further analysis (e. g. temporal profiles). Furthermore, global distribution of pixels and percentage of residuals within the LSA SAF accuracy requirement levels (Table 1) are computed.

Temporal Consistency

The realism of the temporal variations and the precision of the products are assessed over the LANDVAL network of sites plus additional sites with availability of temporal ground measurements. LSA SAF temporal variations are compared to those of the references (satellite-based and ground-based).

Error evaluation: accuracy, precision and uncertainty

Commonly, accuracy represents systematic errors and often is computed as the statistical mean bias (B), i. e., the difference between the short-term average measured value of a variable and the true value. The short-term average is the average of a sufficient number of successive measurements of the variable under identical conditions, such that the random error is negligible relative to the systematic error. The latter can be introduced by instrument biases or through the choice of remote sensing retrieval schemes (GCOS-200, 2016).

Precision or repeatability is the “*closeness of the agreement between the results of successive measurements of the same measurand carried out under the same conditions of measurement*” (JCGM, 2014). Commonly, precision represents the dispersion of product retrievals around their expected value and can be estimated by the standard deviation of the difference (STD) between retrieved satellite product and the corresponding reference estimates.

Uncertainty is a “parameter, associated with the result of a measurement that characterizes the dispersion of the values that could reasonably be attributed to the measurand” (JCGM, 2014). Uncertainty includes both systematic and random errors and can be estimated by the Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD).

In addition to these metrics, other statistics are useful to evaluate the goodness of fit between two datasets including linear model fits. For this purpose, Major Axis Regression (MAR) is computed instead Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) because is specifically formulated to handle error in both of the x and y variables (Harper, 2014). In case of LAI, CEOS LPV recommends RMSD as the overall performance statistic to evaluate the accuracy, due to limitation in the temporal availability of ground datasets (Fernandes et al., 2014). It should be noted that strong and/or multiple outliers affect the classical metrics described above (i. e., B and STD): in such cases using the median deviation (MD) instead of the mean bias to estimate systematic error and the median absolute deviation (MAD) as a measure of precision is more suitable. Table 2 summarises the metrics used for accuracy, precision, uncertainty (APU), and the goodness of the fit between LSA SAF products and reference products.

Table 2. Validation metrics for product validation. ‘x’ refers to reference products, and ‘y’ to product under evaluation.

Statistics	Comment
N	Number of samples. Indicative of the power of the validation.
B	Mean Bias. Difference between average values of x and y. Indicative of accuracy and offset. Bias (%) is the relative mean bias in percentage.
MD	Median deviation between x and y. CEOS LPV good practice reporting the accuracy. MD (%) is the relative MD in percentage.
STD	Standard deviation of the pair differences. Indicates precision. STD (%) is the relative STD in percentage.
MAD	Median absolute deviation between x and y. CEOS LPV good practice reporting the precision. MAD (%) is the relative MAD in percentage.
RMSD	Root Mean Square Deviation. RMSD is the square root of the average of squared errors between x and y. CEOS LPV good practice for reporting uncertainty. RMSD (%) is the relative RMSD in percentage.
MAR	Slope and offset of the Major Axis Regression linear fit. Indicative of possible bias.
R	Correlation coefficient. Indicates descriptive power of the linear accuracy test. Pearson coefficient is used.

Note that two aspects of the precision should be also evaluated: inter-annual and intra-annual precision (Fernandes et al., 2014). To further investigate precision the following metrics are computed:

- Anomalies of an upper and lower percentile of variable are indicators of **inter-annual precision** (i.e., dispersion of variable values from year to year) (Fernandes et al., 2014). It can be assessed providing the median absolute deviation of anomalies of upper (95th) and lower (5th) percentiles between consecutive years. Upper and lower percentiles are chosen to reduce the effect of inter-annual variability. Note that cultivated sites are not considered in this analysis to avoid effects related to agricultural practices (e.g., crop rotation from one year to another year).
- **Intra-annual precision** (smoothness) corresponds to temporal noise assumed to have no serial correlation within a short time period. In this case, the anomaly of a variable from the linear estimate based on its neighbours can be used as an indication of intra-annual precision. It can be characterized (Weiss et al., 2007) as follows: for each triplet of consecutive observations, the absolute value of the difference between the center $P(d_{n+1})$ and the corresponding linear interpolation between the two extremes $P(d_n)$ and $P(d_{n+2})$ is computed:

$$\delta = \left| P(d_{n+1}) - P(d_n) - \frac{P(d_n) - P(d_{n+2})}{d_n - d_{n+2}} (d_n - d_{n+1}) \right| \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where ‘d’ stands for day of year

The distribution of the intra-annual precision is analysed, and the median δ value is used as a quantitative indicator of the intra-annual precision (Fernandes et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2019). Hence, the lower median of δ values, the higher the intra-annual precision.

Stability

Stability is the property of an instrument to provide similar measurements when the measurand remains constant in time. Analysis of multidecadal long-term stability of satellite data records is a key requirement for the applicability of these products for climate observation. This is of particular importance in data records created from different satellite sensors, as the transition from one sensor to another may create artificial changes in the time series (Mota et al., 2021). While stability assessment has not been addressed in depth for biophysical variables, other EO community has defined stability as the change in bias (apparent error) over a time period (Merchant, 2013).

As we do not have long-term ground reference against to compare with the EPS VEGA estimates, we use satellite-based references instead. Hovmöller plots of the bias during the 2008-2021 period between EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1 (based on SPOT/VGT and PROBA-V) and MODIS C6.1 over LANDVAL sites are computed to assess temporal changes in the bias. The first year was excluded from this analysis because unstable EPS BRDF inputs in the initial six months degraded VEGA product quality. Moreover, mean values over LANDVAL sites were computed during the period. The Mann-Kendall test (Mann, 1945; Kendall 1975) is a non-parametric test for identification of trends in time series and is widely used in remote sensing

(Tuli et al., 2019). The Mann-Kendall test allows to assess if a set of data values is increasing or decreasing over time and if the trend is statistically significant. Note that a trend in the time series data could indicate a change in the stability of the sensors. The test analyzes the sign of the difference between each value to all the subsequent time period values. To conclude that the null hypothesis (H0) is true, the time series data must be independent random variables and equally distributed. To deduce that the alternative hypothesis (H1) is true, the time series data must follow a monatomic trend. In this work, the Man-Kendall test is evaluated at the 0.05 significance level (it means that there is 5% of probability that the trend which is observed is because of chance).

H0: No monotonic trend or random observations.

H1: Monotonic trend, with sign of the trend according to the Mann-Kendall statistic S, calculated from the temporally sorted dataset:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sgn}(Y_j - Y_i)$$

Where Y_i and Y_j are the observations for the decade i and j , respectively and n is the total number of decades.

The sign function is defined as:

$$\text{sgn}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases}$$

A positive S indicates that later values tend to be larger than earlier values and it means that the values are increasing and vice versa. If the p -value of S is less than the significance level (in the study 0.05), there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis H_0 and to conclude that time series have a trend, otherwise, if the p -value is greater than the empirical significance level, the test cannot conclude that a monotonic trend exists.

The Mann-Kendall test provides also the slope of the mean values data record estimated with the Theil-Sen robust linear estimator (Fernandes and Leblanc, 2005). The slope is used to estimate the change per decade of the vegetation variable. Note that LANDVAL sites over deserts were removed from all this Mann-Kendall computation as MODIS C6.1 does not provide values over these sites for the sake of fair comparisons.

Conformity testing

Conformity testing is the process to determine whether an estimated quantity is within the range of tolerable values or not (Widlowski, 2015). Up to now, in most validation studies, satellite and references uncertainties have not been considered in the conformity testing. In those cases, the

data points which are within the tolerance intervals (requirements) are considered conform and the others are non-conform. This decision rule is known in metrology as “shared risk” or “simple acceptance” conformity testing. The shared risk approach can provide a first assessment of the conformity with requirements. Nevertheless, if product and references uncertainties are known, the “guarded acceptance” testing is preferable for a better understanding of the compliance of requirements, considering the uncertainty of the apparent error (Camacho et al., 2024a).

As our ground references and some satellite references do not have well characterized their uncertainties, the shared risk or simple acceptance conformity test (conform / non-conform) has been evaluated for the three level of requirements (optimal, target, threshold). Therefore, if the apparent error or bias (EPS value – reference) lies within the specified requirement, the product estimate is conform or compliant; otherwise, it is non-conform. Finally, the percentage of compliant retrievals with $|\text{bias}| < \text{requirement}$ is computed, and then the compliance of EPS VEGA-R with the target accuracy requirement is assessed (VEGA-R shall meet at least 50% Target requirement).

Summary of the quality assessment procedure:

Table 3 summarizes the quality criteria, validation metrics, reference data and spatio-temporal coverage used for the validation of EPS VEGA data record (VEGA-R). Note that the period used for the validation and product intercomparisons can be slightly different depending on the criteria evaluated or the reference data availability. For most of them a four-year period 2013-2016 has been selected, corresponding to the two last years of the DR based on MetOp-A and the two first years of the DR based on MetOp-B. This allows us to focus on the transition from MetOp-A to MetOp-B. Then, the 6 complete years (2015-2020) of DR concomitant with NRT was used for the intercomparison with the operational products. For assessing temporal consistency, the period was extended to the full series (2007- mid 2021) for calibration sites, and to the period with available multi-temporal ground references (2013-2019). For the inter-annual precision, the period includes 2007-2020 (as 2021 data are only available for half the year). Accuracy assessment covers periods with ground data (2000-2020 for DIRECT 2.1 and 2013-2019 for GBOV V2). For the stability assessment, the first year of the DR (2007) was excluded, as BRDF input during its initial months is unstable, resulting in less reliable vegetation estimates(see

Annex I). The assessed period for stability therefore covers 13 years (01/2008–12/2020). Satellite products must be compared over a similar spatial support area and temporal support period. Thus, reference products (CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1, C3S V3) were re-sampled to the EPS projection. The product intercomparison and direct validation was performed at 3x3 EPS pixel of spatial resolution. It should be noted that ground-based references are provided covering a slightly lower area of 3 km x 3 km.

Regarding the temporal support period, the analysis was performed at 10 days temporal frequency, the closest decade has been selected for comparing EPS products and satellite references at the centre of the temporal composite window. For this purpose, the Z_age ancillary layer of EPS product was used as follows:

- For the spatial consistency (maps of residuals) and statistical analysis, an assumption of a Z_age of 10 days was done. This is explained by the fact of the large computational cost to find the equivalent date of each individual pixel between EPS and references using the Z_age value of EPS over the whole region. It means that the real date of EPS product corresponds to 10 days before to the date in the file name (end of the temporal composite). Based on this hypothesis, pixels with Z_age values greater than 20 were also discarded for the computation of residuals and associates scatter-plots, as an additional quality criterion.
- For the temporal consistency and error evaluation, the EPS actual date was computed as the difference between the product date in the file name (end of the temporal window) and the Z_age value (average of dates corresponding to clear scenes).

Table 3. Summary of the quality assessment procedure.

Quality Criteria	Product evaluated	Reference Product	Sampling (period)
Product Content	EPS VEGA-R	None	Global (2013-2016)
	Visual inspection of global maps (product and error estimates), Quality flag and Z_age.		
Completeness	EPS VEGA-R	CLMS V1, C3S V3	Global & LANDVAL (2013-2016)
	Global maps of missing values. Temporal evolution of missing over LANDVAL.		
Spatial Consistency	EPS VEGA-R	CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1	Global (2013-2016)
	Global maps and histograms of residuals.		
Temporal Consistency	EPS VEGA-R	CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1, C3S V3 GBOV V2	LANDVAL (2013-2016) GBOV V2 (2013-2019) Calibration Sites (2007-

			mid 2021)
	Qualitative inspection of temporal variations.		
Intra-annual precision (smoothness)	EPS VEGA-R	CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1, C3S V3	LANDVAL (2013-2016)
	Histograms of the smoothness. Median δ values.		
Inter-annual precision	EPS VEGA-R	CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1	LANDVAL (2008-2020)
	Median absolute anomaly of 95 th percentile and 5 th percentile for consecutive years.		
Error evaluation (product intercomparison)	EPS VEGA-R	MetOp-A vs. MetOp-B	LANDVAL (2013-2016)
		EPS VEGA NRT	LANDVAL (2015-2020)
		CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1, C3S V3	LANDVAL (2013-2016)
	Scatter-plots and metrics (R, RMSD, Bias, S, MAR). Box-plots of uncertainty metrics (Bias) per biome.		
Error evaluation (direct validation)	EPS VEGA-R	CEOS DIRECT 2.1	DIRECT 2.1 (2007-2020)
		GBOV V2	GBOV V2 (2013-2019)
	Scatter-plots and metrics (R, RMSD, Bias, S, MAR).		
Stability	EPS VEGA-R	CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1	LANDVAL (2008-2020)
	Hovmöller plots, mean and change/decade (%)		
Conformity testing	EPS VEGA-R	CEOS DIRECT 2.1	DIRECT 2.1 (2007-2020)
		GBOV V2	GBOV V2 (2013-2019)
		CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1, C3S V3	LANDVAL (2013-2016)
	Simple acceptance test of conformity with LSA SAF requirement		

4.2 SATELLITE REFERENCE PRODUCTS

This section provides an overview of the retrieval algorithms of the satellite products used in this exercise. Table 4 summarizes the quality flag information used to discard pixels flagged as low quality, out of range or invalid, or providing large errors due to different reasons.

Table 4. Quality flag information used to filter low quality or invalid pixels.

Product	Criteria for suboptimal quality
EPS VEGA-R	<p>Quality flag: Bit 7=1 (Suspect, poor quality)</p> <p>EPS Error: LAI_Err> 1.5, FVC_Err> 0.15, FAPAR_Err> 0.15</p> <p>Z_age: Z_age> 20</p>
CLMS V1	<p>Quality flag: Sea (bit 1), Snow (bit 2), Input status out of range or invalid (bit 6), LAI/FAPAR/FCOVER out of range or invalid (bits 7, 8, 9), B2 saturated (bit 10), B3 saturated (bit 11).</p>
MODIS C6.1	<p>FparLai_QC: bits 5,6,7 corresponding to SCF_QC (five-level confidence score):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 010 (2): Main (RT) method failed due to bad geometry, empirical algorithm used. • 011 (3): Main (RT) method failed due to problems other than level 2. • 100 (4): Pixel not produced at all, value could not be retrieved).
C3S V3	<p>retrieval_flag: bit 0 (obs_is_fillvalue), bit 6 (tip_untrusted), bit 7 (obs_unusable)</p>

4.2.1 CLMS SPOT/VGT AND PROBA-V COLLECTION 1KM VERSION 1 (CLMS V1)

Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) Collection 1 km Version 1 provides LAI, FAPAR and FVC biophysical variables at global scale covering the period from 1999 to May 2014 from SPOT/VGT (in version V1.4) (Baret et al., 2013) data and from June 2014 to June 2020 from PROBA-V data (in version 1.5).

The algorithm of CLMS V1 relies on neural networks trained to generate the “best estimates” of LAI, FAPAR, and FCOVER obtained by fusing and scaling of MODIS and CYCLOPES products (Baret et al., 2013). The methodology is made of 3 steps: 1) the generation of the training dataset; 2) the neural network calibration; 3) the application of the network. This version 1 has been chosen even if a Collection 1 km Version 2 is also available, as the algorithm of version 1 is based on a “similar” concept in terms of compositing window (20–30 days), BRDF normalization (both are based on normalized reflectances), and the use of machine-learning algorithms (EPS trained on synthetic data and CLMS V1 on existing products). On the other hand, CLMS 1km V2 (Verger et al., 2023) is based on daily retrievals with smoothing and gap-filling techniques using a climatology. Thus, V2 delivers interpolated and climatology-driven estimates whose associated uncertainty is not fully represented. This represents an additional level of processing, which reduces comparability with EPS LSA SAF. By choosing V1 as reference, we use a satellite product that follows a comparable retrieval approach to EPS VEGA.

Therefore, if good consistency is achieved with CLMS V1, confidence in EPS VEGA performance is reinforced.

The accuracy of SPOT/VGT CLMS V1 products was evaluated against CEOS DIRECT reference data, with RMSD of 0.7/0.08/0.09 for LAI/FAPAR/FVC variables (Camacho et al., 2013), showing a slight overestimation of the FVC product over cropland sites. CLMS V1 based on PROBA-V shows good continuity with SPOT/VGT V1 (Sánchez-Zapero et al., 2015). RMSD between retrievals from SPOT/VGT and PROBA-V was 0.3/0.03/0.04 for LAI/FAPAR/FCOVER, with almost no mean bias (~2%). The quality assessment of CLMS V1 based on PROBA-V (Camacho et al., 2017) showed however slight negative bias for FAPAR and positive for FVC in comparison with SPOT/VGT. The comparison with upscaled ground data showed an RMSD of 0.52 for LAI, 0.11 for FAPAR and 0.14 for FCOVER, showing a bias for FVC for higher values over cropland sites (Camacho et al., 2017). Other studies (Nestola et al., 2017) showed very good results for FAPAR over a deciduous beech forest site in Italy with an RMSD of 0.04 and a slight negative bias (-0.02) as compared to ground data.

4.2.2 NASA MODIS MOD15A2H COLLECTION 6.1 (MODIS C6.1)

TERRA MODIS C6.1 LAI and FAPAR products (MOD15A2H) are available at a spatial resolution of 500 m over a sinusoidal grid and a step of eight days since 2000 at <https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov>.

The algorithm retrieves LAI and FAPAR values given sun and view directions, Bidirectional Reflectance Factor (BRF) for each spectral band, uncertainties (i.e., relative stabilized precision, (Wang et al., 2001)) in input BRFs, and land cover classes based on an 8-biome classification map (Myneni et al., 2002; Yang et al., 2006). The operational LAI/FAPAR algorithm consists of a main algorithm that is based on 3D radiative transfer equation and a backup algorithm. By describing the photon transfer process, this algorithm links surface spectral BRFs to both structural and spectral parameters of the vegetation canopy and soil (Asrar and Myneni, 1991; Ross, 1981). Given atmosphere corrected BRFs and their uncertainties, the algorithm finds candidates of LAI and FAPAR by comparing observed and modelled BRFs that are stored in biome type specific Look-Up-Tables. All canopy/soil patterns for which observed and modelled BRFs differ within biome-specified thresholds of uncertainties (e.g., 30% and 15% for red and near-infrared bands, respectively, for forest biomes) are considered candidate solutions and the mean values of LAI and FAPAR from these solutions are reported as outputs. The mean and dispersion of LAI/FAPAR candidates are reported as retrieval and its reliability, respectively. The law of energy conservation (reflectance, transmittance and absorbance sum up to unity) and the theory of spectral invariance are two important features of this main algorithm (Knyazikhin et al., 1999).

The main algorithm may fail to localize a solution if uncertainties of input BRFs are larger than threshold values or due to deficiencies of the RT model that result in incorrect simulated BRFs.

In such cases, a backup empirical method based on relations between NDVI and LAI/FAPAR (Knyazikhin et al., 1998; Myneni and Williams, 1994) is utilized to output LAI/FAPAR with relatively poor quality (called the backup algorithm). It should be noted that pixels computed by this backup solution are discarded from the analysis.

The accuracy assessment performed over 45 FAPAR ground measurements from CEOS DIRECT data showed an overestimation of both Collection 5 and 6 FAPAR products over sparsely vegetated areas (Yan et al., 2016). Comparisons with SPOT/VGT Collection 1km V1 products showed similar spatial distributions at a global scale (Yan et al., 2016), and temporal comparisons for the 2001–2004 period showed that the products properly captured the seasonality of different biomes, except in evergreen broadleaf forests.

The improvements of C6.1 respect to C6 are:

- The Version 6.1 Level-1B products have been improved by undergoing various calibration changes that include: changes to the response-versus-scan angle approach that affects reflectance bands for Aqua and Terra MODIS, corrections to adjust for the optical crosstalk in Terra MODIS infrared bands, and corrections to the Terra MODIS forward look-up table update for the period 2012 - 2017.
- A polarization correction has been applied to the L1B Reflective Solar Bands.

4.2.3 C3S SPOT/VGT AND PROBA-V MULTI-SENSOR VERSION 3 (C3S V3)

C3S LAI and FAPAR multi-sensor V3 products are produced every 10 days for almost 40 years of satellite observations from NOAA/AVHRR (September 1981 to December 2005) at around 40 km of spatial resolution and from SPOT/VGT (April 1998 to May 2014) and PROBA-V (October 2013 to June 2020) at 1 km resolution. They are available at <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.7e59b01a>.

C3S V3 products are generated using the Two-stream Inversion Package (TIP) algorithm (Pinty et al., 2006), which provides effective LAI and FAPAR along with their uncertainties by applying the TIP to visible (VIS) and near infrared (NIR) broadband albedos (Blessing et al., 2021). The input data is surface albedo V2.0 (Carrer et al., 2021) which incorporates harmonized measurements from the platforms NOAA-[7...17], SPOT-[4-5] and PROBA-V. This harmonization is performed at BRDF retrieval, which uses a common BRDF climatology data from SPOT/VGT as prior information for all sensors with two main objectives: (i) reduce the gaps in time series, and (ii) introduce multi-sensor information in each albedo estimation to increase homogeneity among the datasets derived from each sensor.

C3S LAI/FAPAR multi-sensor V3 reached an overall good quality (Sánchez-Zapero et al., 2021). The comparison with ground data showed a clear tendency to underestimate ground-based DIRECT 2.1 and GBOV upscaled maps, mainly for the highest ranges (i.e., forest) of LAI. The

main limitations of the products are: i) the high density of points with C3S LAI and fAPAR V3 very close to 0 (winter at northern latitudes); ii) some temporal noise over equatorial targets; and iii) the systematic negative bias compared with the rest of references for LAI as C3S provides effective LAI. Since C3S V3 based on TIP provides effective LAI values, the C3S LAI field is not used as a satellite-based reference for quantitative comparisons with EPS estimates. C3S LAI values are only shown for qualitative inspection of temporal profiles.

4.3 IN-SITU BASED REFERENCE PRODUCTS

4.3.1 DIRECT 2.1

Ground references of high quality are needed to validate satellite-based products. The DIRECT 2.1 database (Camacho et al., 2024b) constitutes a major effort of the international community to provide suitable ground reference for the validation of LAI, FAPAR and FVC satellite products. DIRECT V2.1 is endorsed by CEOS and hosted in the CEOS cal/val portal (<https://calvalportal.ceos.org/lpv-direct-v2.1>) compiles ground references averaged values over a 3 km x 3 km area.

The ground data collected over elementary sampling units was upscaled using high spatial resolution imagery following CEOS LPV guidelines to properly account for the spatial heterogeneity of the site. Ground measurements included in the first version (DIRECT) were resulting from several international activities including VALERI, BigFoot, SAFARI-2000, CCRS, Boston University and ESA campaigns compiled by S. Garrigues (Garrigues et al., 2008), and later ingested in the CEOS LPV OLIVE tool (Weiss et al., 2014) for accuracy assessment. DIRECT databased was revised to remove those sites without understory measurements (Fernando Camacho et al., 2013) and after that DIRECT was expanded with the inclusion of ImagineS sites (Camacho et al., 2021). The CEOS LPV DIRECT 2.1 database is the last update including 44 new sites from China (Fang et al., 2019; Song et al., n.d.) and 2 sites from ESA FRM4Veg (Brown et al., 2021), with a total of 176 sites around the world (7 main biome types) and 280 LAI values, 128 FAPAR and 122 FCOVER values covering the period from 2000 to 2021.

It should be noted that the uncertainty associated to LAI reference maps is expected to be around 1 LAI units for dense forest (Fernandes et al., 2003) or around 0.5 for croplands (Martínez et al., 2009), which is around 20%. Therefore, with the available ground truth reference data is difficult to achieve the strict optimal requirements on accuracy for LAI LSA SAF products. Further research on FAPAR and FCOVER should be conducted to evaluate the uncertainty attached to ground reference maps, which could be also slightly higher than goal requirements for satellite-based products.

4.3.2 GBOV

As part of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, the Ground-Based Observations for Validation (GBOV) service aims at facilitating the use of observations from operational ground-based monitoring networks and their comparison to Earth Observation products. In case of LAI, FAPAR and FCOVER, GBOV distributes reference measurements (RMs) mostly coming from data collected in the US National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON), and the corresponding upscaled land products (LPs) over 3 km x3 km at decametric and hectometric resolution.

Currently, GBOV provides the LPs version V3, which calibrates RTM-based retrievals with ground measurements to generate the upscaled maps. The previous version of upscaled maps (LP V2) was based on multitemporal transfer functions between vegetation indexes and ground references (Lerebourg et al., 2019). V3 has some advantages as compared to V2. For instance, viewing and illumination angles are considered in the model, so temporal variations in sun-sensor geometry can be better accounted for, whilst the variety of soil spectra used in the RTM simulations helps reduce the impact of the soil background (Brown et al., 2021). However, V3 has also some theoretical limitations as compared to V2:

- 1) The use of the PROSAIL RTM could favour comparisons with satellite-based products using the same retrieval principles (i.e., inversion of one-dimensional radiative transfer models) instead of those using three dimensional models (e.g., MODIS products) even if PROSAIL is calibrated with ground references.
- 2) The calibration function used between RTM outputs and ground data is generic for forest and non-forest site types, instead of being site dependent as in CEOS LPV upscaled maps (DIRECT 2.1) or in previous GBOV V2. This is a simplification that does not account for site structural differences (e.g., clumping) in the calibration function, which may have a large impact in LAI for some forest sites.

To further analyse the impact of using generic calibration function for all sites (forest or non-forest), a comparison between RMs and LPs V3 has been conducted over visually homogeneous sites at 300 m. Large differences were found between LPs V3 and RMs (see Figure 2) in some cases, demonstrating that a generic calibration approach (LP V3) is not well suited for all sites as LPs calibrated with RMs should be close (no bias) to RMs over spatially homogeneous sites.

Figure 2. Temporal profiles of GBOV V3 LPs (red) vs RMs (black) over two NEON sites. LSA SAF EPS VEGA-R data is shown in blue.

As large differences were found between GBOV V3 LPs and RMs, an evaluation of the differences between LPs and RMs was made for both available versions (GBOV V3 and GBOV V2) over sites visually homogeneous at 300 m (Figure 3). RMSD values show that GBOV V2 (site-dependent calibration) provides better results than GBOV V3 (generic calibration) in most cases, with mean RMSD of 0.86, 0.09 and 0.11 for LAI, FAPAR and FVC respectively (improving V3 mean RMSD values mainly for LAI). Systematic bias, not shown for sake of brevity, is also better in V2 in those sites with better RMSD values. It should be noted that V3 presents other issues (e.g., stability issues due to calibration function changes in subsequent subversions (from v3.1 to v3.3) that apply to different periods or the limited availability of LPs values over sparse areas due to poor representativeness of soil spectra in the RTM model) that support the selection of V2 for accuracy assessment. Therefore, GBOV V2 is selected to validate LSA SAF EPS VEGA-R products, and attention should be paid to some sites with larger RMSD, therefore a quality control has been conducted and described hereafter.

Figure 3. Root Mean Square Deviations between GBOV LPs (V2 in pink, V3 in blue) and RMs over visually homogeneous sites at 300 m. Dashed pink and blue lines represent the mean RMSD for V2 and V3, respectively.

GBOV V2 provides data from 2013 to 2019 over 23 sites with a temporal frequency typically of 10 days. A quality control has been performed to filter out sites with large errors. Firstly, GBOV LPs provided systematic lower values as compared with other satellite products for sparse sites (CPER, JORN, MOAB, SRER and STER). These sites provide very low values in GBOV. Therefore, a processing of the NEON Digital Hemispherical Photographs (DHP) images used to derive the GBOV RM over these sites has been made by EOLAB using the CAN-EYE software (Weiss et al., 2017). This CAN-EYE processing revealed a systematic underestimation of the GBOV RMs in periods where DHP reveals the presence of green vegetation. In fact, GBOV V2 aggregates several of these sparse sites (JORN, MOAB, NIWO, ONAQ) for the transfer function

due to their limited seasonality and range in RM values (Lerebourg et al., 2019). As we cannot recalibrate the GBOV LPs we have removed these sites for the validation. Additionally, few other sites were discarded: DSNY as it is very heterogeneous and close to an urban area, GUAN was discarded because RMs does not provide understory data over this evergreen broadleaf forest site resulting in a clear underestimation of the canopy LAI. Finally, NIWO was also discarded because NEON DHPs (over three locations) were over bare areas and are not representative of the vegetation over this mountain area at the AVHRR pixel level. The final 15 GBOV sites selected for validation are listed in Table 5. Note that BLAN and LAJA sites were not included in the validation with RMs (see Figure 3) as they are heterogeneous sites and are not suitable for direct comparison at 300m.

Table 5. Summary of GBOV V2 quality-controlled sites used for validation of EPS data.

#	Site ID	Name	Lat (°)	Lon (°)	Land cover type	DOYmin - DOYmax
1	BART	Bartlett Experimental Forest	44.0639	-71.2873	MF	121-292
2	BLAN	Blandy Experimental Farm	39.0602	-78.0716	CUL	4-338
3	DELA	Dead Lake	32.5417	-87.8039	DBF	8-362
4	HARV	Harvard Forest	42.5378	-72.1715	OF	114-300
5	JERC	Jones Ecological Research Center	31.1948	-84.4688	NLF	8-362
6	LAJA	Lajas Experimental Station	18.0213	-67.0769	HER	2-338
7	ORNL	Oak Ridge	35.9641	-84.2826	OF	93-312
8	ONAQ	Onaqui Ault	40.1776	-112.4524	SHR	2-338
9	OSBS	Ordway Swisher Biological Station	29.6839	-81.9934	NLF	2-338
10	SCBI	Smithsonian Conservation Biology Institute	38.8929	-78.1395	OF	92-304
11	SERC	Smithsonian Environmental Research Center	38.8902	-76.5601	OF	81-294
12	STEI	Steigerwaldt Land Services	45.5089	-89.5864	DBF	122-300
13	TALL	Talladega National Forest	32.9505	-87.3932	NLF	8-362
14	UNDE	Underc	46.2340	-89.5375	OF	120-300
15	WOOD	Woodworth	47.1282	-99.2414	HER	4-338

The quality indicators associated to the LP maps were considered for the accuracy assessment: only those GBOV V2 pixels in which more than 70% of the corresponding high-resolution pixels are valid were used. In addition, GBOV V2 LPs produced outside of the minimum and maximum Day Of Year (DOY) of the measurements were discarded, to prevent errors due to the limited extrapolation capabilities of the empirical transfer functions.

5 QUALITY ASSESSMENT RESULTS

5.1 PRODUCT CONTENT VERIFICATION

The spatial consistency of the product content was visually checked with animations of the maps of the different product layers at 1/6 of its original resolution along the 2013-2016 period where retrievals are based on Metop-A (2013-2014) or MetOp-B (2015-2016) AVHRR observations. Each FVC, LAI and FAPAR product contains 4 layers:

- Vegetation field (FVC, LAI or FAPAR).
- Error estimates (FVC, LAI or FAPAR).
- Quality control information.
- The “age” of the information (Z_{age}), representing the difference in days between the date indicated in the file name of the distributed product and the date representing the average of dates corresponding to clear scenes used to make the product over the composite period.

Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 show some examples of FVC, LAI and FAPAR global maps (and their associated ancillary layers) for different dates: 2014.02.25, 2015.06.25 and 2016.10.25, respectively.

Figure 4. Maps of EPS VEGA-R FVC and ancillary FVC_ERR, QF and Z_{Age} layers for 2014.02.25 based on MetOp-A.

Figure 5. Maps of EPS VEGA-R LAI and ancillary error estimate, quality flag and Z_Age layers for 2015.06.25 based on MetOp-B.

Figure 6. Maps of EPS VEGA-R FAPAR and ancillary error estimate, quality flag and Z_Age layers for 2016.10.25 based on MetOp-B.

The visual inspection of the EPS VEGA-R maps shows:

- Reliable and consistent distributions of FVC, LAI and FVC retrievals (and error estimates) are found over the globe during the 2013-2016 period without finding any strange patterns or artefacts regardless of the satellite sensor used for the retrieval.
- Quality flag provides expected values according to documentation (see [RD-4]). As expected, pixels were not processed in the following cases: water (ocean or continental), no EPS observation (Bit 3 = 0), high probability of undetected snow (Bit 4 = 1), snow (Bit 5 = 1), mixture snow (Bit 6 = 1). Pixels processed flagged as 'suspect' or 'low quality' can be easily identified when quality flag digital values are greater than 127.

- Z_Age values are typically between 0 and 20, showing higher values (up to the maximum range of 127 days) over northern regions in winter and tropical areas.

5.2 ASSESSMENT OF THE INTERNAL CONSISTENCY OF THE DATA RECORD

5.2.1 CONSISTENCY BETWEEN ESTIMATES FROM METOP-A AND METOP-B SATELLITES

Figure 7 shows the scatter-plots of EPS VEGA-R products between two different periods (2015-2016 vs. 2013-2014) to assess the impact of the transition from MetOp-A to MetOp-B. It should be noted that cultivated sites are removed from this analysis because of crop rotation practices can lead to large differences between consecutive years. Further analyses are provided in the section dedicated to temporal consistency (section 5.5) and to the stability of the data record (section 5.9).

Figure 7. EPS VEGA-R FVC, LAI and FAPAR scatter-plots between MetOp-B (2015-2016) and MetOp-A (2013-2014) periods. Computation over LANDVAL sites excluding crop sites. Dashed lines correspond to optimal, target and threshold LSA SAF requirements on accuracy. BQ stands for best quality retrievals.

There is no major impact in the vegetation variables for the transition from MetOp-A to MetOp-B data, with mean bias and median deviations of 0 for the three variables and perfect linear fit (1:1 line) for FAPAR and FVC and almost 1:1 for LAI. RMSD values can be mainly associated to the inter-annual natural variability and remaining stochastic noise.

5.2.2 CONSISTENCY BETWEEN DR AND NRT ESTIMATES

Figure 8 shows the scatter-plots of EPS VEGA NRT products versus the VEGA-R under evaluation for 2015-2020 period (i.e., MetOp-B). As observed, optimal agreement is found with bias and MD close to 0%, perfect fit along the 1:1 line, and correlation of 1 between both datasets with 99% of differences within target requirement on accuracy. This demonstrates the optimal consistency of the DR with the operational NRT production. Therefore, NRT products can be used to expand this DR beyond 2021 without introducing bias.

Figure 8. EPS VEGA FVC, LAI and FAPAR scatter-plots between DR and operational NRT products for MetOp-B 2015-2020 period. Computation over LANDVAL sites. Dashed lines correspond to optimal, target and threshold LSA SAF product requirements. BQ stands for best quality retrievals.

5.3 PRODUCT COMPLETENESS

Figure 9 displays the annual global maps of the percentage of missing values of EPS VEGA-R for 2013 considering all pixels, and best quality (BQ) pixels applying the quality flags (Table 4). Figure 10 shows the completeness of reference products (BQ) for benchmarking. For the sake of brevity, these results are displayed for FAPAR as LAI and FVC show same results, and the 2013 year (very similar results are found for the other years). On the other hand, the temporal evolution of missing values for EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1 and C3S V3 products is displayed in Figure 11, computed over LANDVAL sites. The computation of gaps was performed considering all pixels and best quality pixels. It should be noted that MODIS C6.1 products are not included in this comparison as these products do not provide values over desert areas. Besides, the MODIS algorithm incorporates a backup solution to fill most of the gaps of the main algorithm.

Figure 9. Map of the percentage of missing values of FAPAR for 2013 year: EPS VEGA-R all pixels (top) and EPS VEGA-R BQ pixels (bottom).

Figure 10. Map of the percentage of missing values of FAPAR for 2013 year: CLMS V1 BQ (top), MODIS C6.1 BQ (middle) and C3S BQ (bottom).

Figure 11. Temporal variation of the percentage of missing values for EPS VEGA-R (blue), CLMS V1 (purple) and C3S V3 (green) products for 2013-2017 period. Computation for LANDVAL sites considering all pixels (continuous lines) and best quality (BQ) pixels (dashed lines).

The analysis of the product completeness shows:

- The lack of EPS retrievals reaches up to 100% over polar regions mainly due to snow and persistent cloudiness, as for most reference products based on polar-orbiting satellites (Camacho et al., 2013). This is one known limitations of products derived from optical sensors aboard polar orbiting satellites.
- On the other hand, remarkably good completeness and temporal continuity is found in the tropical, subtropical and warm temperate regions improving the completeness of all reference satellite products (Figure 10), and, therefore, mitigating known deficiencies in current operational products over cloudy areas.
- Similar temporal evolution of missing values is found between EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1, showing the maximum value (~40%) during the wintertime in Europe and the minimum (~3%) during summertime in Europe. C3S V3 shows similar temporal trend but displays lower number of missing values as C3S provide estimates over snow/ice pixels, whereas other products mask out pixels identified as snow or ice.

5.4 SPATIAL CONSISTENCY

In this section, global distribution of residuals between EPS VEGA-R and reference CLMS V1 and MODIS C6.1 products are evaluated. Table 6 shows the linear equations used to compute the residuals. These equations are based on the major axis regression (MAR) linear trends, which are computed using LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period. It should be noted that, in case of the comparison of LSA SAF DR with CLMS V1, residuals are close to differences between products as MAR relationships are close to 1:1 line (particularly for FAPAR).

Table 6. Major axis regression (MAR) relationship between LSA SAF VEGA-R and reference (CLMS V1 and MODIS C6.1) products. Computation over LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period.

	LSA SAF VEGA-R vs. CLMS V1	LSA SAF VEGA-R vs. MODIS C6.1
FVC	$y=0.95x+0.01$	-
LAI	$y=0.96x+0.03$	$y=0.88x+0.14$
FAPAR	$y=0.99x-0.01$	$y=1.14x-0.08$

5.4.1 LSA SAF EPS VEGA-R vs COPERNICUS CLMS V1

Figure 12 presents the maps of residuals and the maps of percentage of cases within the predefined accuracy levels (Table 4) between EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1 vegetation products for a selected date in June 2014 for products based on MetOp-B. The histograms of residual per month for the year 2014 for products based on MetOp-A, and the percentage of residuals within accuracy requirements are also shown in Figure 13 for the whole 2013-2016 period (including observations from both MetOp-A and MetOp-B).

Figure 12: Residual maps (left) and maps of percentage of residuals showing LSA SAF requirements between EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1 for June 2014. From top to bottom: FVC, LAI and FAPAR.

Figure 13: Left side: Histograms of FVC (top), LAI (middle) and FAPAR (bottom) residuals between EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1 for 2014 year at monthly basis. Right side: Percentage of residuals within the optimal, target and threshold levels of consistency, computed as average values per month during the 2013-2016 period.

The spatial consistency analysis between EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1 show:

- For FVC:
 - Both products are spatially consistent over large areas around the globe. Typically, around 70-75% of pixels over the globe are fulfilling the target uncertainty level. Pixels where residuals are non-conforming LSA SAF requirements represent between 17%-20% of land pixels and are largely distributed over northern regions and tropical regions where larger uncertainties are typically found.
- For LAI:
 - Consistent values between EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1 are found over large areas, showing residuals typically between ± 1 LAI units for almost the whole globe (~91%) except over some areas located in northern latitudes and over the equatorial belt.
 - The percentage of cases within LAI target consistency level is generally ranging between 75% and 85% and goes up to ~90% including threshold level.
- For FAPAR:
 - Generally good consistency is found over large areas, with more than ~82% of residuals lower than ± 0.1 . Higher residuals are found over equatorial zones and northern regions as for the other variables.
 - Between 70% and 75% of FAPAR residuals are matching the target spatial consistency level. Pixel non-conform to LSA SAF requirements represents around 15%-20% of global data.

5.4.2 LSA SAF EPS VEGA-R vs MODIS C6.1

Figure 14 presents the maps of residuals and the maps of percentage of cases within the predefined uncertainty levels (Table 1) between EPS VEGA-R and MODIS C6.1 LAI and FAPAR products for a selected date in April 2014. The percentage of residuals within the optimal, target and threshold predefined uncertainty levels of consistency are also shown in Figure 15 for the whole 2013-2016 period.

Figure 14: Residual maps (left) and maps of percentage of residuals showing LSA SAF requirements between EPS VEGA-R and MODIS C6.1 for April 2014. From top to bottom: LAI and FAPAR

Figure 15: Left side: Histograms of LAI (top) and FAPAR (bottom) residuals (over vegetated pixels) between EPS VEGA-R and MODIS C6.1 for 2014 year at monthly basis. Right side: Percentage of residuals (over vegetated pixels) laying the optimal, target and threshold levels of consistency, computed as average values per month during the 2013-2016 period.

EPS VEGA-R vs MODIS C6.1 residual maps show:

- For LAI:
 - Residuals are typically between ± 1 LAI units for most of the BQ vegetated pixels (79%). Note that negative residual values were found over equatorial forests whereas positive residuals were found over other regions. This change of the sign of residual is partly explained because the MODIS algorithm is biome dependent and provides larger values in EBF than in other biomes.
 - The percentage of cases within LAI goes up to $\sim 70\%$ for the target level. Pixels non-conforming LSA SAF requirements represent around 30% of vegetated pixels (desert are not included), distributed over large areas (i.e., equatorial areas, -Southeast Asia, and Europe).
- For FAPAR:
 - Larger spatial discrepancies are found. Residual values between EPS and MODIS C6.1 are typically ranging between ± 0.2 .
 - Generally, around 55% of residuals are within the target level (excluding bare areas). Between 40 and 45% of the vegetated pixels show poor spatial consistency (i.e., residuals non-conforming threshold levels on accuracy).

5.5 TEMPORAL CONSISTENCY

The main objective of this section is to evaluate the temporal consistency of EPS VEGA-R products, comparing their temporal variations with CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3 vegetation products over LANDVAL sites for the years 2013-2016, and with ground-based maps over GBOV V2 sites for the years 2013-2019. Satellite products (BQ retrievals) are displayed at their native spatial resolution and centred at their temporal composite window. In case of EPS, the date was computed as the difference between the last date of the composite (file name) and the Z_{age} . Several examples for each main biome type are displayed from Figure 16 to Figure 22.

Figure 16. Temporal profiles of EPS VEGA-R (blue), CLMS V1 (pink for VGT and purple for PBV), C3S V3 (light green for VGT and dark green for PBV, LAI corresponds to an effective LAI) and MODIS C6.1 (orange) vegetation best quality products over four selected evergreen broadleaved forests. For sites with availability of ground data, GBOV V2 LPs are displayed using black dots. Vertical bars display the EPS product error.

Figure 17. Same as in Figure 16 but for deciduous broadleaved forests.

Figure 18. Same as in Figure 16 but for needle-leaf forests.

Figure 19. Same as in Figure 16 but for cultivated.

Figure 20. Same as in Figure 16 but for shrublands.

Figure 21. Same as in Figure 16 but for herbaceous.

Figure 22. Same as in Figure 16 but for sparse and bare areas. Note the different scale used in FVC (as compared to FAPAR) to better display the small variations.

The inspection of temporal profiles shows the following:

- For EBF (Figure 16), both EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1 show very similar temporal trend, as well as with GBOV V2 ground references. Noisy temporal profiles are found for evaluated EBF sites with unrealistically large variations in some cases (e.g., LANDVAL #107). Nevertheless, EPS VEGA improves notably the references MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3, which show much noisier temporal trajectories (see MODIS C6.1 profiles). Besides, C3S LAI products show very low values even for an effective LAI estimate. The noise in

EBF retrievals is a well-known problem in equatorial rain forests due to cloud contamination.

- For DBF (Figure 17), good temporal consistency was found with reference data in most cases (see LANDVAL #28, #621). However, EPS VEGA-R products show late ending season compared with other satellite references in some cases (e.g., LANDVAL #210, GBOV DELA). The comparison with ground data in DELA site shows a better agreement of EPS VEGA with GBOV references.
- For NLF (Figure 18), most of the examined temporal profiles show good temporal consistency with satellite and GBOV data. However, EPS shows discrepancies in some sites (e.g., LANDVAL #291) during the maximum development of the vegetation period. In these sites, it should be noted that the error associated with the estimate is large, indicating to the user that the reliability of these measurements is lower. This larger uncertainty bars in NLF sites located over northern latitudes can be partly explained by the larger error associated with the BRDF retrieval over northern latitudes (i.e., due to less available observations, residual cloud and snow contamination and large solar zenith angles among others).
- Similarly, EPS VEGA-R shows overall very good temporal consistency with the reference products for Cultivated (Figure 19) site, capturing properly seasonal and inter-annual variations. Slight discrepancies at the end of the season were found in few cases (see LANDVAL #516).
- For shrublands (Figure 20) and Herbaceous (Figure 21), good temporal consistency is generally found between EPS VEGA-R, satellite products and ground data.
- Finally, for sparse and bare areas (Figure 22), seasonal trajectories close to zero are found for almost all the evaluated sites. Over calibration sites, we found that EPS VEGA-R shows a peak corresponding to the first and second decades of MetOp-B (i.e., January 2015) before stabilising in very low values (see for instance Egypt#1 in Figure 21). This effect is occurring at the input BRDF/Albedo level, as the Albedo algorithm start to ingest data from MetOp-B and then stabilize after few decades [RD-3].

5.6 PRECISION

5.6.1 INTRA-ANNUAL PRECISION

Figure 23 shows the histograms of the intra-annual precision (δ , so-called smoothness). It should be noted that only concomitant sites providing valid data are used in this study and, therefore, desert sites are not considered as MODIS does not provide data for this biome.

Figure 23. Histograms of delta function (smoothness) for EPS VEGA-R (blue), CLMS V1 (purple), C3S V3 (green) and MODIS C6.1 (orange) over concomitant LANDVAL sites providing data during the 2013-2016 period. FVC (left), LAI (middle) and FAPAR (right).

These results indicate:

- EPS VEGA-R shows median δ values (i.e., indicator of intra-annual precision) of 0.011 for FVC and FAPAR and 0.47 for LAI. As compared to other references, intra-annual precision of EPS VEGA-R is closer to CLMS V1 (best precision) than to MODIS (worst precision) median δ values.

5.6.2 INTER-ANNUAL PRECISION

To investigate the inter-annual precision of the products, median absolute anomalies (MAD) of the upper 95th and lower 5th percentiles between consecutive years were computed over LANDVAL sites excluding croplands for best quality retrievals. Figure 24 shows the inter-annual precision between pair of consecutive years for EPS VEGA-R for the 2007-2020 period for FVC (identical to FAPAR) and LAI. The median value across the whole period is considered as indicator of inter-annual precision.

Figure 24. Median absolute deviation (MAD) of 5th and 95th percentiles between consecutive years over LANDVAL for EPS VEGA-R (2007-2020 period). FVC (left) and LAI (right).

Table 7 shows the summary of the inter-annual precision indicator for all products under study for the 2007-2020 period.

Table 7. Inter-annual precision of EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, C3S V3 and MODIS C6.1. MAD stands for Median Absolute Deviation.

	Median of MAD (5th, 95th) 2007-2020		
	FVC	LAI	FAPAR
EPS VEGA-R	0.03	0.12	0.03
CLMS V1	0.02	0.09	0.02
MODIS C6.1	-	0.10	0.03
C3S V3	-	-	0.02

These results indicate:

- EPS VEGA-R shows overall inter-annual precision of 0.03 for FVC and FAPAR, and 0.12 for LAI, with quite similar results from different years. This is quite similar to what is found for MODIS products. CLMS V1 provides slightly better inter-annual precision metric values than EPS.
- The transition from MetOp-A to MetOp-B (year 2015 vs. year 2014) does not have an impact, as the median absolute deviation (5th, 95th) is similar to the median value of the whole period.

The inter-annual precision for 2008 vs 2007 shows significantly larger MAD values than the median for the whole period for FVC (similar FAPAR) and larger values for LAI. This is explained by the fact that during the first months of the 2007, the BRDF input data were not yet fully stabilized, and the VEGA parameters were therefore impacted (see, for instance, the higher values over calibration sites in

Annex I). Consequently, the lower inter-annual precision for the 2008 vs 2007 is associated with the lower quality of 2007 BRDF input data.

5.7 ERROR EVALUATION WITH SATELLITE-BASED REFERENCES

5.7.1 OVERALL CONSISTENCY

To evaluate the spatiotemporal consistency of EPS VEGA-R with reference products (CLMS V1, MODIS 6.1 and C3S V3), scatter-plots and validation metrics were computed over LANDVAL sites during the 2013-2016 period for best quality pixels (Table 4). Figure 25, Figure 26 and Figure 27 show the scatter-plots for FVC, LAI and FAPAR whilst relevant statistics are provided in Table 8, Table 9 and Table 10.

Figure 25. Scatter-plots between EPS VEGA-R FVC products versus CLMS V1 computed over best quality retrievals over LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period. Color bars represent density of points, green, blue and brown lines indicate the optimal, target and threshold levels, respectively. BQ stands for best quality.

Figure 26. Scatter-plots between EPS VEGA-R LAI products versus CLMS V1 (left) and MODIS C6.1 (right) computed over best quality retrievals over LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period. Color bars represent density of points, green, blue and brown lines indicate the optimal, target and threshold levels, respectively. BQ stands for best quality.

Figure 27. Scatter-plots between EPS VEGA-R FAPAR products versus CLMS V1 (top-left),

MODIS C6.1 (top-right) and C3S V3 (bottom) computed over best quality retrievals over LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period. Color bars represent density of points, green, blue and brown lines indicate the optimal, target and threshold levels, respectively. BQ stands for best quality.

Table 8. Performance statistics of FVC product intercomparison. Computation over best quality retrievals over LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period.

EPS VEGA-R FVC vs. CLMS V1	
R	0.96
Bias (%)	~ -0.01 (-1.5%)
MD (%)	~ 0.01 (0.4%)
STD (%)	0.08 (25.9%)
MAD (%)	0.03 (10.9%)
RMSD (%)	0.08 (26.0%)
MAR	$y=0.95x+0.01$

Table 9. Performance statistics of LAI product intercomparisons. Computation over best quality retrievals over LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period.

LAI		
	EPS VEGA-R vs. CLMS V1	EPS VEGA-R vs. MODIS C6.1
R	0.95	0.87
Bias	-0.01 (-1.2%)	-0.01 (-0.8%)
MD	~ 0.00 (-0.1%)	-0.05 (-4.3%)
STD	0.46 (37.4%)	0.73 (58.1%)
MAD	0.12 (9.4%)	0.24 (18.7%)
RMSD	0.46 (37.4%)	0.73 (58.1%)
MAR	$y=0.96x+0.03$	$y=0.88x+0.14$

Table 10. Performance statistics of FAPAR product intercomparisons. Computation over best quality retrievals over LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period.

FAPAR			
	EPS VEGA-R vs. CLMS V1	EPS VEGA-R vs. MODIS C6.1	EPS VEGA-R vs. C3S V3
R	0.97	0.92	0.85

Bias	-0.01 (-3.0%)	-0.02 (-6.3%)	0.08 (27.1%)
MD	>-0.01 (-0.6%)	-0.04 (-11.4%)	0.04 (12.4%)
STD	0.07 (20.7%)	0.11 (27.5%)	0.16 (53.2%)
MAD	0.03 (9.3%)	0.07 (19.1%)	0.08 (26.2%)
RMSD	0.07 (20.9%)	0.11 (28.2%)	0.18 (59.7%)
MAR	$y=0.99x-0.01$	$y=1.14x-0.08$	$y=1.34x-0.01$

Main findings of the overall consistency of EPS VEGA-R versus reference satellite products are:

- For FVC, the comparison with CLMS V1 shows high correlation ($R=0.96$) and overall discrepancies (RMSD) of 0.08, with no systematic differences (mean bias and MD close to 0.0) and linear fit very close to the 1:1 line. This demonstrates the good consistency between EPS VEGA and CLMS V1.
- For LAI:
 - High correlation ($R=0.95$), low overall discrepancies (RMSD of 0.46) and no systematic bias (-0.01) is found in the comparison with CLMS V1. This demonstrates the good consistency between EPS VEGA and CLMS V1 LAI.
 - Larger discrepancies (RMSD=0.73, $R=0.87$) are found in the comparison with MODIS C6.1. A tendency to provide higher values than MODIS was observed for LAI values lower than 3 whereas the opposite trend was observed for LAI values higher than 3. Consequently, the linear fit shows positive offset (0.14) and slope of 0.88.
- For FAPAR:
 - Very good correlation of 0.97, with overall discrepancies (RMSD) of 0.07 and almost no mean bias (-0.01) with MAR fit close to 1:1 was found with CLMS V1. This reveals good consistency of EPS and CLMS V1 FAPAR products.
 - In the comparison with MODIS C6.1, overall discrepancies of 0.11, correlation of 0.92 and negative mean bias of -0.02 (-6.3%) is found. EPS provides lower values than MODIS C6 for lower ranges whereas the opposite trend was observed for the higher FAPAR ranges. It should be noted that MODIS FAPAR shows a positive bias for very low values (F. Camacho et al., 2013), with MODIS FAPAR starting around 0.1.
 - The comparison with C3S V3 FAPAR shows the worst agreement, with a non-linear distribution of points, C3S FAPAR values are higher than EPS for low values but much lower for high values. The underestimation of C3S FAPAR for

high values is confirmed in the comparison with GBOV (see Figure 36). This results in large uncertainties (RMSD of 0.18), and systematic mean error (bias) of 0.08 (27%). The slope of the linear fit (1.34) also reveals the larger values provided by EPS for high values.

5.7.2 ANALYSIS PER BIOME TYPE

This section presents the analysis of the bias per biome type between EPS VEGA-R and references CLMS V1, MODIS 6.1 and C3S V3 products. Violin plots, computed over LANDVAL sites during the 2013-2016 period for best quality pixels, are presented in Figure 28, Figure 29 and Figure 30 for FVC, LAI and FAPAR.

Figure 28. Violin plots of the bias per biome type between EPS VEGA-R FVC products versus CLMS V1 computed over best quality retrievals over LANDVAL sites for 2013-2016 period. In each violin, red bars indicate median values, black horizontal lines stretch from 25th to 75th percentile of the data. Red dashed line indicates the median deviation.

Figure 29. As in Figure 28 for EPS VEGA-R LAI products versus CLMS V1 (left) and MODIS C6.1 (right).

Figure 30. As in Figure 28 for EPS VEGA-R FAPAR products versus CLMS V1 (top left), MODIS C6.1 (top right) and C3S V3 (bottom).

Main findings are:

- For FVC, MD close to zero is found in the comparison with CLMS V1 regardless the biome type.
- For LAI:
 - The comparison with CLMS V1 shows, again, MD close to zero for most biome type, and slightly negative for forest sites (mainly NLF).
 - Similarly, EPS and MODIS C6.1 shows bias close to zero for all biome type except for EBF (MD around -1), where MODIS provides higher values with 50% of the bias ranging between -0.5 and -2.
- Finally, for FAPAR:

- The comparison between EPS and CLMS V1 shows MD close to zero for all biome type except for NLF showing a negative bias (EPS < CLMS) with median values around -0.08. A slight negative bias is also observed for OF site.
- EPS and MODIS show slightly positive differences for DBF and cultivated and negative differences for the other biomes. This was partly explained due to the positive bias of MODIS FAPAR for low values (herbaceous, shrublands or sparsely vegetated sites)..
- In case of the comparison of EPS and C3S, positive bias is found for forest cases (in particular, large deviations are observed for EBF) and cultivated, and bias close to zero for the rest of biomes.

5.8 ERROR EVALUATION WITH IN-SITU BASED REFERENCE PRODUCTS

5.8.1 COMPARISON WITH CEOS DIRECT 2.1

, Figure 32 and Figure 33 show the scatter-plots between the satellite products under study and the CEOS DIRECT 2.1 ground-based reference maps, available during the 2007-2020 period. The relevant statistics of the accuracy assessment of EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3 are presented in Table 11.

Figure 31. Comparison of satellite best quality FVC products (EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1) with DIRECT 2.1 ground-based maps. Dashed lines correspond optimal, target and threshold accuracy requirements levels around de 1:1 line, and continuous red line corresponds to the linear fit using major axis regression (MAR). In the legend, R (crosses) stands for Rice crops.

Figure 32. As in for LAI products (EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1 and MODIS C6.1).

Figure 33. As in for FAPAR products (EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3).

Table 11. Performance of EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, MOD15A2H C6.1 and C3S V3 products against reference DIRECT 2.1 ground-based maps for best quality retrievals.

		2007-2020				
		EPS VEGA-R	CLMS V1	MODIS C6.1	C3S V3	
FVC	N	59			-	-
	R	0.86	0.88	-	-	
	B	0.10 (22.3%)	0.14 (29.4%)	-	-	
	MD	0.11 (24.3%)	0.15 (31.1%)	-	-	
	STD	0.11 (25.1%)	0.13 (28.4%)	-	-	
	MAD	0.12 (25.9%)	0.16 (34.0%)	-	-	
	RMSD	0.15 (33.6%)	0.19 (40.9%)	-	-	
	MAR	$y=0.01+1.22x$	$y=-0.03+1.43x$	-	-	
	% Optimal	18.6	28.8	-	-	
	% Target	28.8	32.2	-	-	
	%Threshold	42.4	35.6	-	-	
LAI	N	104			-	
	R	0.79	0.56	0.41	-	
	B	0.34 (14.5%)	0.47 (19.7%)	-0.10 (-4.5%)	-	
	MD	0.29 (12.3%)	0.31 (12.8%)	-0.06 (-2.7%)	-	
	STD	0.80 (34.6%)	1.24 (52.0%)	1.30 (61.9%)	-	
	MAD	0.44 (18.9%)	0.89 (37.2%)	0.73 (34.5%)	-	
	RMSD	0.87 (37.5%)	1.33 (55.6%)	1.31 (62.0%)	-	
	MAR	$y=0.19+1.07x$	$y=0.02+1.21x$	$y=-0.16+1.03x$	-	
	% Optimal	31.7	22.1	18.3	-	
	% Target	56.7	40.4	36.5	-	
	%Threshold	69.2	48.1	52.9	-	
FAPAR	N	45				
	R	0.88	0.93	0.91	0.87	
	B	0.10 (21.0%)	0.08 (14.4%)	0.05 (10.4%)	-0.03 (-8.5%)	
	MD	0.10 (21.8%)	0.08 (18.0%)	0.05 (11.6%)	-0.03 (-7.1%)	
	STD	0.10 (22.2%)	0.07 (15.7%)	0.08 (17.8%)	0.09 (22.6%)	
	MAD	0.12 (24.5%)	0.08 (18.0%)	0.07 (16.1%)	0.07 (16.1%)	
	RMSD	0.14 (29.2%)	0.11 (23.4%)	0.09 (20.6%)	0.10 (24.2%)	
	MAR	$y=0.06+1.0x$	$y=0.05+1.07x$	$y=0.04+1.02x$	$y=-0.02+0.96x$	
	% Optimal	20.0	28.9	40.0	37.8	
	% Target	31.1	48.9	53.3	57.8	
	%Threshold	44.4	68.9	73.3	73.3	

The accuracy assessment over DIRECT 2.1 upscaled maps shows:

For FVC:

- An overall uncertainty (RMSD) of 0.15 is found for EPS VEGA-R, with a tendency to overestimate (mean bias=0.1, MAR slope=1.22) ground-based references. EPS VEGA provides better accuracy and uncertainty than CLMS V1 (bias= 0.14, RMSD=0.19) as compared to DIRECT 2.1 data. Note however that the accuracy of ground-based FVC estimates is partially compromised by the limited footprint, which may result in an underestimation of intermediate ground-based estimates (Yin et al., 2022).

For LAI:

- EPS VEGA-R product shows an overall uncertainty (RMSD) of 0.87, with positive mean bias (0.34). EPS shows improved overall uncertainty than CLMS V1 (RMSD=1.33) and MODIS C6.1 (RMSD = 1.31), with also better correlation. MODIS provides lower systematic bias (-0.1) and MD (-0.06), but the lowest precision (larger scattering).

Finally, for FAPAR:

- EPS VEGA-R product shows an overall uncertainty of RMSD=0.14 and systematically higher values than DIRECT 2.1 (mean bias and MD of 0.1) upscaled references. The other satellite FAPAR products shows better accuracy than EPS VEGA-R with DIRECT sites.

It should be noted that most of the DIRECT 2.1 data corresponds to cropland sites, which indicates that the accuracy assessment with DIRECT 2.1 is mostly representative of the accuracy of the products over agricultural areas. As crop areas are heterogeneous, larger discrepancies are expected due to differences between the footprint of the AVHRR system (3 x 3 pixels; pixel \geq 1.1 km) and the 3 km x 3 km area of the ground-based map. On the contrary, GBOV V2 quality-controlled data is more representative of homogeneous forest sites. Accuracy assessment with GBOV is discussed in the next section.

5.8.2 COMPARISON WITH GBOV V2 LPS

Figure 34, Figure 35 and Figure 36 show the scatter-plots between the satellite products under study and the 16 quality-controlled GBOV V2 LPS selected covering the 2013-2019 period. The relevant statistics of the accuracy assessment of EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3 are presented in Table 12.

Figure 34. Comparison of satellite best quality FVC products (EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1) with GBOV V2 ground-based maps. Dashed lines correspond optimal, target and threshold accuracy requirements levels around de 1:1 line, and the red line corresponds to the linear fit using MAR.

Figure 35. As in Figure 34 for LAI products (EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1 and MODIS C6.1).

Figure 36. As in Figure 34 for FAPAR products (EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3).

Table 12. Performance of EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3 best quality products against reference GBOV V2 ground-based maps

		2013-2019				
		EPS VEGA-R	CLMS V1	MODIS C6.1	C3S V3	
FVC	N (sites)	677 (15)			-	-
	R	0.89	0.87	-	-	
	B	0.02 (3.6%)	0.03 (5.3%)	-	-	
	MD	0.02 (4.0%)	0.06 (9.4%)	-	-	
	STD	0.12 (20.0%)	0.14 (22.8%)	-	-	
	MAD	0.06 (10.3%)	0.12 (19.0%)	-	-	
	RMSD	0.12 (20.3%)	0.14 (23.4%)	-	-	
	MAR	y=0.06+0.93x	y=0.04+0.99x	-	-	
	% Optimal	52.6	30.3	-	-	
	% Target	64.5	45.2	-	-	
	%Threshold	70.5	56.0	-	-	
LAI	N (sites)	454 (13)			-	
	R	0.90	0.83	0.85	-	
	B	-0.26 (-10.9%)	-0.33 (-14.2%)	-0.26 (-11.0%)	-	
	MD	-0.19 (-8.0%)	-0.16 (-6.8%)	-0.14 (-5.9%)	-	
	STD	0.72 (30.5%)	0.91 (39.2%)	0.90 (37.9%)	-	
	MAD	0.49 (20.9%)	0.58 (24.8%)	0.52 (22.1%)	-	
	RMSD	0.77 (32.4%)	0.97 (41.6%)	0.93 (39.4%)	-	
	MAR	y=-0.04+0.91x	y=-0.07+0.90x	y=-0.23+0.99x	-	
	% Optimal	32.2	30.4	26.4	-	
	% Target	61.7	49.3	55.7	-	
	%Threshold	79.1	66.5	66.5	-	
FAPAR	N (sites)	441 (13)				
	R	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.80	
	B	-0.03 (-4.5%)	-0.01 (-2.1%)	-0.02 (-3.1%)	-0.13 (-23.0%)	
	MD	-0.03 (-5.4%)	-0.01 (-1.0%)	-0.03 (-4.2%)	-0.17 (-29.7%)	
	STD	0.11 (18.7%)	0.11 (18.7%)	0.12 (19.8%)	0.17 (30.3%)	
	MAD	0.07 (11.2%)	0.07 (11.4%)	0.09 (14.0%)	0.17 (31.1%)	
	RMSD	0.12 (19.2%)	0.12 (18.8%)	0.12 (20.1%)	0.21 (38.0%)	
	MAR	y=0.04+0.89x	y=0.09+0.84x	y=0.10+0.81x	y=0.06+0.70x+	
	% Optimal	48.8	49.2	39.7	11.6	
	% Target	67.8	64.2	53.5	20.6	
	%Threshold	75.5	73.2	67.3	32.7	

The comparison of satellite products versus GBOV V2 shows:

For FVC:

- EPS VEGA-R products show an overall uncertainty (RMSD) of 0.12, with positive mean bias ($B=0.02$, $\sim 4\%$) and a tendency to provide higher values than GBOV V2 for non-forest sites. The same tendency is observed for CLMS product.
- EPS VEGA-R improves CLMS V1 accuracy and uncertainty. CLMS shows a clear overestimation of FVC GBOV for high values in forests, in agreement with results obtained in previous validation studies (Camacho et al., 2017).

For LAI:

- EPS VEGA-R products show an overall uncertainty (RMSD) of 0.77, with negative mean bias of -0.26 as MODIS. The scatter-plot reveals that negative bias is dominant in forest sites whereas the opposite trend occurs in non-forest sites.
- EPS shows better agreement with GBOV V2 than CLMS V1 (RMSD = 0.97) and MODIS C6.1 (RMSD = 0.93) displaying also better correlation. CLMS V1 and MODIS C6.1 show the same tendency in the sign of the bias (positive for non-forests and negative for forests).

For FAPAR:

- EPS VEGA-R product shows RMSD of 0.12, as CLMS and MODIS products, with a negative mean bias (and media deviation) of -0.03. All satellite products typically provide higher values than GBOV V2 LPs for non-forest cases and the opposite trend for forest cases.

5.9 STABILITY

To investigate the stability of the EPS VEGA data record, Hovmöller plots of the bias between EPS VEGA-R and two reference satellite products (MODIS and CLMS) data over LANDVAL sites are shown for LAI (Figure 37) and for FAPAR (Figure 38). The Hovmöller plot of the bias for FVC between EPS and CLMS is shown Annex II.

For LAI, the differences between the EPS CDR and CLMS LAI displayed a stable regular temporal pattern until 2019 where the bias increases notably from north to south. However, the pattern of the bias between EPS and MODIS is very stable along the whole period. Therefore, it can be concluded that the observed increase of differences between EPS and CLMS in 2019 and 2020 is introduced by the CLMS dataset. The same pattern of the bias can be observed for FVC product (see Annex II). In fact, the 2019 and 2020 are the last years of the PROBA-V operational phase, and the orbital drift of PROBA at the end of its mission life introduce several drifts in the PROBA-V surface reflectance (Niro, 2021) used to generate CLMS LAI.

Similarly, Hovmöller plots of bias between EPS FAPAR and reference products shows very stable latitudinal patterns across the whole period. In this case, it can be also observed a slight increment of the bias with CLMS at the end of the PROBA operational life (year 2020). In the comparison with MODIS, the pattern of the bias is almost identical for the period EPS data based on MetOp-A (2008-2014) than for the period based on MetOp-B (2015-2020), which again confirms the good stability of the EPS VEGA data record.

Figure 37. Hovmöller plots of the LAI bias between: (top) EPS VEGA vs CLMS V1, (bottom) EPS VEGA vs MODIS C6.1.

Figure 38. Hovmöller plots of the FAPAR bias between: (top) EPS VEGA vs CLMS V1, (bottom) EPS VEGA vs MODIS C6.1.

Finally, Figure 39 shows the mean value of EPS and the reference satellite products computed over LANDVAL sites for concomitant best quality retrievals. The Man-Kendall test was computed and the change per decade estimated (

Table 13).

- LSASAF EPS VEGA - R (Slope/year:1.5e-03) p-value=0.000 Mann-Kendall result: increasing
- CLMS V1 (Slope/year:2.9e-03) p-value=0.000 Mann-Kendall result: increasing

- LSASAF EPS VEGA - R (Slope/year:-3.5e-04) p-value=0.624 Mann-Kendall result: no trend
- CLMS V1 (Slope/year:1.4e-04) p-value=0.936 Mann-Kendall result: no trend
- MOD15A2H C61 (Slope/year:-2.1e-03) p-value=0.108 Mann-Kendall result: no trend

- LSASAF EPS VEGA - R (Slope/year:5.7e-04) p-value=0.002 Mann-Kendall result: increasing
- CLMS V1 (Slope/year:2.5e-05) p-value=0.918 Mann-Kendall result: no trend
- C3S V3 (Slope/year:3.7e-03) p-value=0.000 Mann-Kendall result: increasing
- MOD15A2H C61 (Slope/year:3.7e-04) p-value=0.016 Mann-Kendall result: increasing

Figure 39. Mean value and Mann-Kendall test for EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3 best quality concomitant retrievals over LANDVAL for FVC (top), LAI (middle) and FAPAR (bottom) products.

Table 13. Change per decade of the mean value and Mann-Kendall test results of EPS VEGA-R, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3 over LANDVAL concomitant best quality retrievals for FVC, LAI and FAPAR products.

Variable	Product	Change/decade	S	p-value	Decision
FVC	EPS VEGA-R	0.015	712	<0.001	Increasing
	CLMS V1	0.029	1124	<0.001	Increasing
LAI	EPS VEGA-R	-0.0035	-44	0.624	No Trend
	CLMS V1	0.0014	8	0.936	No Trend
	MODIS C6.1	-0.021	-142	0.108	No Trend
FAPAR	EPS VEGA-R	0.0057	274	0.002	Increasing
	CLMS V1	0.0003	10	0.918	No Trend
	MODIS C6.1	0.0037	212	0.016	Increasing
	C3S V3	0.037	1502	<0.001	Increasing

This analysis shows:

- EPS VEGA-R products show stable pattern of the bias with MODIS reference products. EPS VEGA-R improves stability of CLMS, as the observed changes in the bias are attributable to the effect of the well-known orbital drift of PROBA towards the end of its operational phase (June 2020).
- EPS VEGA provides very similar mean values and seasonal variations as compared to MODIS and CLMS products. The latter shows an impact in the transition from SPOT/VGT to PROBA-V in the FVC, as higher mean values are clearly observed since 2014 (change to PROBA-V) onwards. The Mann-Kendall test results show that both EPS VEGA-R and CLMS V1 time-series tend to increase being the change per decade much lower for EPS (0.015) than for CLMS (0.029) affected by the transition from SPOT to PROBA-V.
- The Man-Kendall test for LAI and FAPAR shows very similar results for EPS and for MODIS. In case of LAI, both shows a negative change per decade, but this trend is no significant, whereas for FAPAR both EPS and MODIS show a similar in magnitude increasing trend (0.0057 for EPS and 0.0037 for MODIS). Note that for C3S FAPAR product the change per decade is one order of magnitude higher (0.037), which is unrealistically high and maybe also artificially increased by the change of sensor (from SPOT/VGT to PROBA-V).
- In summary, EPS VEGA-R products are stable and fully consistent with the mean values and trends of MODIS products, whereas the other two reference products show systematically higher values when using PROBA-V data as input (since 2014) for some variables.

5.10 CONFORMITY TESTING

This section discusses the conformity testing results of EPS VEGA-R products against the ground-based and satellite-based references used in this validation report. It should be noted that the ground references are limited by its representativeness in terms of biomes and geographical location, in particular, the DIRECT 2.1 database represents mostly cropland sites, and the GBOV database represents mostly forests sites. Conversely, satellite-based references are representing global conditions. Figure 40 and Table 14, Table 15 and Table 16 show the conformity with the three levels (optimal, target and threshold) of LSA SAF accuracy requirements.

Figure 40. Conformity testing of EPS VEGA-R FVC (top left), LAI (top right) and FAPAR (bottom) versus DIRECT 2.1, GBOV V2, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3 according to the LSA SAF optimal, target and threshold product requirements.

Table 14. Conformity testing of EPS VEGA-R versus DIRECT 2.1, GBOV V2, CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 according to the optimal, target and threshold product requirements for FVC products.

EPS VEGA-R FVC vs.					
	DIRECT 2.1	GBOV V2	CLMS V1	MODIS C6.1	C3S V3
% optimal	18.6	52.6	64.7	-	-
% target	28.8	64.5	77.9	-	-
% threshold	42.4	70.5	86.4	-	-

Table 15. Same as in Table 14 for LAI products.

EPS VEGA-R LAI vs.					
	DIRECT 2.1	GBOV V2	CLMS V1	MODIS C6.1	C3S V3
% optimal	31.7	32.2	34.2	20.6	-
% target	56.7	61.7	85.8	72.1	-
% threshold	69.2	79.1	92.2	82.5	-

Table 16. Same as in Table 14 for FAPAR products.

EPS VEGA-R FAPAR vs.					
	DIRECT 2.1	GBOV V2	CLMS V1	MODIS C6.1	C3S V3
% optimal	20.0	48.8	67.7	36.0	39.7
% target	31.1	67.8	80.1	54.2	50.2
% threshold	44.4	75.5	87.7	70.4	58.6

The simple acceptance conformity testing of EPS VEGA-R products shows:

- For FVC, conforming pixels with optimal requirements represents between 20% and 65% depending on the reference, which increases to 30% - 78% for target and to 42% - 86% regarding threshold accuracy level, showing higher conformity with satellite (CLMS) references over a global network, and lower conformity with DIRECT 2.1 (cropland) ground reference, where larger collocation mismatch uncertainties are expected.
- For LAI, conforming pixels with optimal requirements represents between 21% and 34% depending on the reference, increasing to 57% - 86% in case of target level, and up to 70% - 92% for threshold level, which is remarkably good. Similar results are found regardless of the source of reference data.
- For FAPAR, conforming pixels with optimal requirements represents between 20% and 68%, between 31% to 80% for target level, and 44% to 88% for threshold level. For FAPAR, EPS VEGA-R conforming pixels with GBOV are larger than with MODIS or C3S satellite references.
- EPS VEGA-R product compliance with regard to LSA SAF accuracy requirements is superior to CLMS, MODIS and C3S products for the different accuracy level using GBOV (mainly forests) as reference (see section 5.8.2).
- LSA SAF VEGA-R achieves the target accuracy in more than 50% of cases compared with GBOV ground-based references over forests sites and compared with three validated satellite-based references (CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1, C3S V3) over global sampling of sites, thereby meeting the required LSA SAF target accuracy specifications. The only exception was DIRECT 2.1 database where target accuracy was achieved only for LAI.

The lower compliance compared with DIRECT 2.1 can be partly explained by the fact that this database corresponds mostly to cropland sites, which are more heterogeneous; therefore, validation mismatch uncertainties are expected to be larger, particularly given the wide field of view of the AVHRR optics.

It is important to note that uncertainties in the reference and satellite products were not considered, as they are not well characterized in either ground-based or satellite-based references. Therefore, non-conforming pixels may be related to errors in the EPS products or in the references.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The quality assessment of EPS/AVHRR FVC, LAI and FAPAR Data Record (EPS VEGA-R) based on MetOp-A and MetOp-B for the period 2007-2021 was conducted in agreement with the CEOS LPV good practice protocol for validation of LAI products and state-of-the-art of standardized validation of satellite-based bio-geophysical products. After the verification of the product content, the following main criteria were assessed: completeness, spatial and temporal consistency, error evaluation (accuracy, precision and uncertainty) and stability. Two main sources of references were used to evaluate different criteria: satellite references for product intercomparison (CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3) and ground-based maps (DIRECT 2.1 and GBOV V2) for direct validation. In addition, the DR consistency between estimations from MetOp-A and MetOp-B was assessed as well as the consistency of the DR with NRT estimates. Finally, a simple acceptance conformity testing regarding the LSA SAF requirements on accuracy was conducted using the available references.

Main results and conclusions are summarized below:

DR consistency

- FVC, LAI and FAPAR estimations retrieved from sensors aboard MetOp-A and MetOp-B are fully consistent, with regression fit equal to the 1:1 line (bias and MD = 0) over LANDVAL sites (excluding crops), which indicates no impact due to the change of sensor.
- Temporal trajectories also confirm no impact due to the transition from MetOp-A to MetOp-B. Only over some calibration sites a small peak lower than the uncertainty of the estimate can be detected in the first decade of MetOp-B data (January 2015).
- The DR and the operational NRT products based on MetOp-B are also fully consistent with linear fit equal to the 1:1 line, MD of 0 and R=1 over LANDVAL sites. This demonstrates that NRT can be used to expand the data record beyond 2021 without introducing bias.

Product completeness

- EPS VEGA-R completeness is good below 40° latitude and shows poor completeness over northern latitudes (as for reference products). Over tropical and subtropical areas the product shows a remarkable good completeness, which is a clear advantage of EPS VEGA-R as compared to other existing polar-orbiting vegetation products, except those using smoothing and gap-filling techniques.
- The temporal evolution of missing values, evaluated over LANDVAL, showed the maximum value of missing data (~35%) in January, and the minimum (~5%) during June-September.

Spatial consistency

- EPS VEGA-R and CLMS products are spatially consistent over large areas around the globe. More than 70% of residuals fulfil the target accuracy level for FVC and FAPAR, and more than 65% for LAI for the period 2013-2016. Pixels with large residuals (non-conforming threshold requirements) range between 10% and 20% depending on the month. Larger inconsistencies are found in September (towards the end of the growing cycle in northern hemisphere) and over northern latitudes.
- EPS VEGA-R and MODIS present lower spatial agreement with large residuals, for LAI the % of residuals within target level ranges between 55% and 65%, with lower consistency also in September (up to 33% non-conform pixels) for vegetated pixels. For FAPAR, the consistency is worse than for LAI with target level between 50% and 56% for vegetated pixels.

Temporal consistency

- EPS VEGA-R seasonal and inter-annual temporal variations were found temporally consistent with reference satellite products and ground-based GBOV values in most of the evaluated sites (LANDVAL + GBOV), displaying more noise in EBF where the impact of residual clouds is more important. In some cases, EPS shows longer season as compared with satellite references.
- During the first months of the time series based on MetOp-A data, EPS VEGA-R shows abnormal larger values in desertic calibration sites, which tend to zero after several months. Hence, the first months of the EPS VEGA data record should be used with caution.

Intra-annual precision

- EPS VEGA-R intra-annual precision shows (median δ) values of 0.011 for FVC/FAPAR and 0.47 for LAI. Intra-annual precision for EPS is similar to references over LANDVAL, better than for MODIS C6.1 and C3S V3 but slightly worse than CLMS V1.

Inter-annual precision

- EPS VEGA-R shows inter-annual precision of 0.03 for FVC and FAPAR and 0.12 for LAI which is very similar to the rest of satellite products showing slightly better values.
- No impact is found in the transition from MetOp-A to MetOp-B (i.e., 2015 vs. 2014), with similar inter-annual precision than other pair of consecutive years.

Lower inter-annual precision is observed for 2008 compared to 2007, which is attributed to the reduced reliability of estimates during the first half of 2007, due to the lower quality of the BRDF input data in that period.

Error evaluation with satellite-based references

- EPS VEGA-R shows very good performance as compared to CLMS V1 over LANDVAL, with no systematic errors (mean bias and MD very close to zero), and uncertainty (RMSD) of 0.08, 0.46 and 0.07 for FVC, LAI and FAPAR.
- Good agreement was found for all biome type, except for NLF in case of FAPAR where EPS product underestimates CLMS V1 references.
- The comparison of EPS VEGA-R versus MODIS C6.1 shows:
 - RMSD of 0.73 and 0.11 for LAI and FAPAR.
 - Bias close to zero for all biome for LAI except for EBF, where EPS largely underestimates MODIS retrievals. In case of FAPAR, positive bias for DBF and cultivated and negative for the rest of biomes (mainly for NLF).
- Finally, the comparison of EPS VEGA-R versus C3S V3 shows the worst agreement, with RMSD of 0.18 for FAPAR and large positive bias for forest sites (mainly EBF).

Error evaluation with ground-based reference products

- The validation with CEOS DIRECT 2.1 data (mostly croplands) shows:
 - For FVC, EPS showed an uncertainty (RMSD) of 0.15, better than CLMS V1 (RMSD=0.19) with a tendency to overestimate ground references (Bias=0.10).
 - For LAI, EPS showed an uncertainty (RMSD) of 0.87 better than reference products, with positive systematic differences (mean bias = 0.34).
 - For FAPAR, EPS showed positive bias and MD of 0.1 and worst overall uncertainty (RMSD=0.14) than other products: CLMS V1 (RMSD=0.11), MODIS C6.1 (RMSD=0.09) and C3S V3 (RMSD=0.10).
- The validation with GBOV V2 shows:
 - For FVC, EPS VEGA-R showed an overall uncertainty (RMSD) of 0.12, slightly better than CLMS V1 (RMSD=0.14), with slight positive mean bias (0.02).
 - For LAI, EPS VEGA-R showed an overall accuracy of RMSD=0.77, with a tendency to overestimate GBOV V2 for non-forest and the opposite trend for forests (as other reference products). EPS showed slightly improved overall uncertainty than reference products CLMS V1 (RMSD=0.97) and MODIS C6.1 (RMSD=0.93) and similar accuracy.
 - For FAPAR, EPS VEGA-R showed an overall uncertainty of RMSD=0.12, as MODIS and CLMS products and a negative bias of -0.03. All products provide higher values than GBOV V2 for non-forests and the opposite trend for forest

cases.

Stability

- EPS VEGA-R showed very stable pattern of bias as compared to MODIS along the whole period for all latitudes. Differences with CLMS products at the end of the period are related to the impact of the orbital drift of PROBA-V in CLMS products.
- Change of mean values over LANDVAL concomitant best quality data shows very similar values and trends than for MODIS for LAI and FAPAR. As compared to CLMS and C3S, larger discrepancies are explained by the change from SPOT/VGT to PROBA-V data in CLMS and C3S and its orbital drift towards the end of the period.

Conformity testing

- LSA SAF VEGA-R achieves the target accuracy in more than 50% of cases compared with GBOV ground-based references over forests sites and compared with three validated satellite-based references (CLMS V1, MODIS C6.1, C3S V3) over global sampling of sites, thereby meeting the required LSA SAF target accuracy specifications for the three products. Remarkably good results are found as compared to CLMS V1, with up to ~90% of retrievals confirming threshold accuracy requirements for the three variables, and also shows good compliance as compared to GBOV ground references (between 70% and 80% conforming threshold accuracy level).
- Lower percentage of FVC and FAPAR retrievals (around 30%) achieves target accuracy when compared with DIRECT 2.1 FVC and FAPAR. This is partly explained by the database's strong representation of cropland areas, where heterogeneous land cover and large spatial variability typically result in larger collocation mismatch uncertainties considering the wide field-of-view of the AVHRR instrument.

Concluding remarks

The evaluation of EPS VEGA data record (VEGA-R) for the period 2007-2021 has shown overall good quality as compared to satellite-based and ground-based references. EPS VEGA-R shows no impact due to the transition from MetOp-A (2007-2014) to MetOp-B (2015-2021) and is fully consistent with the NRT production, enabling the time series to be extended to the present day. EPS VEGA shows overall good consistency in the comparison with CLMS V1 displaying some underestimation over NLF sites mainly, and lower agreement with MODIS and C3S products particularly over EBF sites. The inspection of temporal profiles reveals reliable seasonal and inter-annual variations as compared to satellite and ground data, with larger discrepancies observed at the end of the growing season with regard to other satellite products. The inter-annual and intra-annual (so-called smoothness) precision of the EPS product is quite similar to that of reference products improving the smoothness of MODIS. Only for the first year

(2007) a lower inter-annual precision was found, as the product are impacted for the lower quality of the BRDF input data during the first months of 2007. User should use this initial half-year period with caution. The accuracy assessment with ground data shows RMSD about 0.12-0.14 for FVC, 0.77-0.87 for LAI and 0.12-0.14 for FAPAR depending on the ground database, improving the accuracy of FVC and LAI of reference satellite products. The EPS VEGA data record shows very good stability as compared to MODIS C6.1, and improved stability as compared to CLMS V1 and C3S V3 data records, both affected by the transition from SPOT/VGT to PROBA-V. EPS VEGA-R meets the LSA SAF target accuracy requirement for more than 50% of the samples when using GBOV ground-based references, and for all samples when using satellite-based references. It also meets the threshold accuracy requirement for up to 80% of the GBOV LAI references and up to 92% of the satellite-based CLMS V1 LAI references, demonstrating that EPS VEGA-R achieves consistently good accuracy across datasets.

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ANNEX I. TEMPORAL PROFILES OF EPS VEGA-R VEGETATION PRODUCTS OVER SELECTED CALIBRATION SITES (2007-2020)

- LSASF EPS VEGA -R - CLMS VGT V1 - CLMS PBV V1 - C3S VGT V3 - C3S PBV V3 - MOD15A2H C61

ANNEX II. HOVMÖLLER PLOT OF THE FVC BIAS BETWEEN EPS VEGA VS CLMS V1.

